

D2.2 - A shared Una Europa strategy for sharing Research Infrastructures and Resources

Una.Resin Project Deliverable D2.2

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

D2.2 - A shared Una Europa strategy for sharing Research Infrastructures and Resources 1

SECTION 1 - Una Europa Strategy and Action plan for sharing and opening up Research and Data Infrastructures..... 4

Executive summary 4

Introduction..... 9

1.1 Pillar 1: Promoting openness of RIs and data infrastructures to foster research collaboration 14

1.2 Pillar 2: Strengthening Research and Data Infrastructure Skills 25

1.3 Pillar 3: Developing a stronger and more integrated Una Europa Research Infrastructure Ecosystem..... 35

SECTION 2 – Annexes: Reports of activities feeding into the Strategy and Action Plan for sharing and opening up research and data infrastructures..... 44

2.1 Report on the co-creation workshop “From mapping to co-creation: towards a Una Europa Strategy and Action Plan for sharing Research Infrastructures and Resources” 44

2.2 Summary of the Open Research survey report and list of webinars..... 73

2.3 Report on the joint workshop with the RiTrainPlus project..... 83

2.4 Pilot actions for sharing RIs: concept, format, evaluation methodology and preliminary results..... 90

Bibliography..... 108

List of abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BUA	Berlin University Alliance
BoD	Board of Directors
CERIF	Common European Research Information Format
COARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
CH	Cultural Heritage
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EEI	European Excellence Initiative
EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
EMMRI	Executive Masters in Management of Research Infrastructures
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EQF	European Qualification Framework
ERA	European Research Area
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
ESMRI	European School for Managers of Research Infrastructures
EUA	European University Association
EUI	European Universities Initiative
EQF	European Qualification Framework
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
IT	Information Technology
KIC	Knowledge and Innovation Communities
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
LA	Learning Activities
LERU	League of European Research Universities
MOOC	Massive Open Online Courses
OER	Open Education Resources
OH	One Health
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
RDM	Research Data Management
R&I	Research and Innovation
RI	Research Infrastructure
RSG	Research Strategy Group
SwafS	Science with and for Society
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats
TM	Transformation Modules

TRT	Transnational Research Teams
SSC	Self-Steering Committee

SECTION 1 - Una Europa Strategy and Action plan for sharing and opening up Research and Data Infrastructures

Executive summary

In line with the actions of the [European Research Area \(ERA\) Policy Agenda](#), the Una Europa 2030 Strategy recognises the **pivotal role of research and data infrastructures for collaborative research** and sets as a strategic aim to promote access to infrastructures and facilities across the Alliance as well as the facilitation of storing, sharing, and accessing data.

Fostering openness, accessibility and interoperability of research and data infrastructures of Una Europa universities will increase the research capacity and **facilitate transnational and interdisciplinary research** across the Alliance. Sharing infrastructures will incentivise **networking and training** of researchers and research managers thereby stimulating research collaboration, and will **support education** for early-career researchers, especially at the doctoral and post-doctoral level. Moreover, this initiative will have multiplying effects by creating educational opportunities based on the use of available RIs, and therefore closely **integrating research with educational activities**.

To achieve this, Una Europa universities need to coordinate efforts to address and overcome legal, financial, organisational, technical and cultural barriers that currently impede the sharing of research and data infrastructures within and across institutions.

It is first of all important to acknowledge that **research infrastructures (RIs)¹ in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)** have unique characteristics. A significant factor to consider is

¹ In the Una.Resin project, Research Infrastructures (RIs) were defined using the [European Commission's definition](#) as "facilities that provide resources and services for research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields" including major scientific equipment or sets of instruments, collections, repositories, archives or scientific data, computing systems and communication networks. As highlighted also in D2.1 "Mapping RIRs and priorities for joint strategy", research infrastructures of universities are strongly embedded in the practices and experience of research, as engines for research data generation, knowledge elaboration and places of sociality as well as training. The RIs ecosystem of universities includes a wide range of infrastructures of different categories, different sizes and across disciplinary fields, and the variety of expertise related to infrastructure management. The accessibility and sharing of these research infrastructures and resources across Una Europa

the variety of management models: RIs can be managed by units, Core Facilities or as part of international projects. Moreover, RIs vary in scale, with small and medium-sized RIs deeply integrated within local ecosystems, while large-scale RIs are more interconnected within the European ecosystem and ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures) initiatives. The interconnectivity between small, medium-sized and large-scale RIs, as well as their alignment with regional and national roadmaps on RIs, are therefore particularly important.

Furthermore, it is important to recognize the critical role played by **data infrastructures** - defined as “ICT infrastructures enabling services for supporting the data life cycle” ([European Open Science Cloud Glossary](#)) - in particular, publication portals and institutional repositories, as well as tools for data transfer and statistics, that are usually centrally managed by universities and available for all researchers. In addition, there are research units that manage research infrastructures that contribute to the research data repository as part of their activities. These types of data facilities’ services are coordinated by an overarching level, which is the centrally managed infrastructure.

Guided by the common long-term ambition of **a joint R&I ecosystem where RIs and data infrastructures are opened and shared across the Alliance**, Una Europa universities will work together to address common challenges, such as the long-term sustainability of RIs, the upskilling of staff managing RIs and data infrastructures (including central and distributed levels), and the legal constraints for opening and sharing infrastructures and data. In particular, Una Europa will support the development of a **common framework of short, medium and long-term actions** aimed at achieving **a stronger Una Europa R&I ecosystem where research and data infrastructures are open and connected**, and **support the advancement of collaborative research and education activities**.

The Una Europa **Strategy and Action Plan for Sharing Research Infrastructures and Resources**, which is part of the overall R&I Strategy (Una.Resin Deliverable 1.2 “Una Europa Research and Innovation Strategy”), is structured around 3 main pillars:

1. Promoting openness of RIs and data infrastructures to foster research collaboration
2. Strengthening Research and Data Infrastructure skills
3. Developing a stronger and more integrated Una Europa Research Infrastructure Ecosystem

These three priorities, that are thoroughly described in Section 1, are based on the activities carried out in the Una.Resin project (Section 2 includes as Annexes the detailed reports of these activities) in collaboration with the Self-Steering Committees (SSCs) Cultural Heritage

Institutions are essential and have a fundamental role to play in the creation of a sustainable, locally embedded and globally articulated R&I ecosystem of universities across the Alliance.

and One Health of Una Europa and in consultation with the Research Infrastructures Clusters and the Open Research Cluster. The Project Steering Committee of Una.Resin provided feedback on the proposed priorities, that were finally approved by the Una Europa Board of Directors and Research Strategy Group.

Pillar 1: Promoting openness of RIs and data infrastructures to foster research collaboration

The **first pillar** is aimed at promoting the openness of RIs and data infrastructures to foster R&I collaboration across the Alliance and beyond, through: (i) an in-depth analysis for identifying barriers and enablers to opening and sharing RIs; (ii) community building processes; (iii) the development of common tools to share information on RIs. These activities will lay a solid foundation for achieving openness and creating synergies across RIs and data infrastructures and will help create meaningful links and collaboration with the stakeholders of the local ecosystem, including non-academic public and private actors as well as the civil society. The proposed actions are the following:

- Take forward the analysis of **barriers**, including an in-depth investigation of costing/business models and other aspects including legal issues, aimed to identify **common enablers and solutions**, resulting in recommendations for an Una Europa Charter for RIs with common guiding principles, with a view to scaling up the analysis and suggesting solutions across different research fields.
- Support the development of a **RIs community** through networking and matchmaking formats in **thematic areas** towards the creation of structured **synergies and virtual thematic networks of RIs**, in, across, and beyond the Alliance; **physical mobility** will be key for the consolidation of this community.
- Support the development of a **Data community** to promote the exchange of best practices among Una Europa **data experts/managers**, with a view to **consolidating FAIR data principles** (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) in compliance with the **EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) recommendations**. Physical mobility will be crucial for building this community and the creation of synergies with other Alliances and European initiatives oriented towards open data will allow Una Europa to play an important and strategic role in the development of EOSC.
- Co-create common **tools to share information on Una Europa RIs**, to facilitate cross-institutional access and visibility, also towards external users including non-academic actors of the private and public sector and the civil society; starting from a blueprint for an Una Europa digital catalogue of RIs, a common portal of services will be developed in the long term.

Pillar 2: Strengthening Research and Data Infrastructure Skills

The **second pillar** addresses the need to strengthen the knowledge and skills of RI and data managers by setting up mutual learning processes and by providing training opportunities for the professional development and upskilling of RIs and the Data community of the Alliance. The proposed actions are the following:

- Implement **mutual learning processes** across the RIs and Data community based on a peer learning approach, starting from the exchange of knowledge and best practices, through virtual connection and physical mobility (for job shadowing and in-person exchange visits), and moving towards **structured mobility and exchange formats**.
- Implement **training activities** for the benefit of the RIs and Data community, based on the analysis of needs and opportunities, including possible synergies with the RiTrain Plus project, towards the development of structured training programmes contributing to the professional development of RI managers and data managers.

Pillar 3: Developing a stronger and more integrated Una Europa Research Infrastructure Ecosystem

The **third pillar** is aimed at developing a stronger and more integrated Una Europa Research Infrastructures Ecosystem by promoting coordinated visions and common principles for sharing RIs across the Alliance and advocating together with other Alliances for an improvement of the funding landscape for RIs, especially oriented to smaller and medium-scale RIs. Building on the results of Pillar 1, this activity will involve all RIs stakeholders but also policy makers in each institution. The proposed actions are the following:

- Formulate coordinated visions for opening and sharing RIs across the Alliance, towards the **promotion of common guiding principles** (i.e., **Una Europa Charter for RIs**) and **awareness raising actions** that can promote a broader cultural change, thus fostering collaborative research.
- Engage in coordinated actions to **advocate for improvements in the RIs policies and funding landscape at European level**, with specific attention to the challenges faced by small-medium sized RIs, in collaboration with other European University Alliances and creating synergies with other networks (e.g., LERU, the Guild).

The proposed framework of actions, structured around the three pillars summarised above, includes **bottom-up participatory initiatives** (e.g., interaction and networking among groups of RIs across the Alliance; mutual learning processes; development of common tools) engaging the academic and professional community, to let specific perspectives, needs and actions emerge from different thematic fields and by different types of RIs and to foster community building. This bottom-up engagement process will also lay the foundation for the co-creation and implementation of common principles for overcoming barriers to sharing RIs. The active

involvement of RIs in the the research and educational activities of the Self-Steering Committees (SSCs) is also particularly crucial: **opening and sharing RIs will support and strengthen research collaborations within and across Focus Areas**, in line with Area of Action n. 1 of the R&I Strategy “Strengthening the Focus Areas” (see Deliverable 1.2).

Moreover, the promotion at institutional level of **coordinated visions and shared principles** for opening and sharing RIs will be key to drive a broader **cultural change** across Una Europa universities. The engagement in joint advocacy actions at European level will be decisive to unlocking the full potential of infrastructures in Una Europa universities and strengthen their specific RIs ecosystems. In particular, as EU policies and funding instruments are mainly oriented towards ESFRI-level research infrastructures, Una Europa can add value in focusing on strengthening the ecosystem of **small and medium-sized research infrastructures**, enhancing their competitiveness and outreach, also through creating or reinforcing linkages with the ESFRI initiatives and national or regional roadmaps. Additionally, as small and medium-size RIs are usually deeply rooted in their local ecosystems, it will be possible to engage a wide community of stakeholders across disciplinary fields, as well as citizens and non-academic actors across all regions of the Una Europa universities.

Both bottom-up and top-down actions foreseen by the three strategic pillars will contribute to the creation of a **common space of knowledge and practices exchange**, supported by **common tools** and by a **community of practice** including broad categories of researchers and research professionals such as research infrastructures experts and managers, data stewards and data infrastructures managers, as well as technical and administrative staff and students. This will also contribute to Area of Action n. 2 of the R&I Strategy “Engaging Researchers Broadly” (cf. Deliverable 1.2) by promoting mobility and community building. These actors will be able to meet, exchange knowledge and good practices, improve their skills, find common solutions, easily access RIs and data infrastructures, and undertake concrete **trans-national and trans-disciplinary collaboration actions in research and education** - therefore contributing to building an **inclusive, innovative and attractive ecosystem** for Una Europa universities.

Introduction

Alignment with EU policies and priorities

In the Una.Resin project, **Research Infrastructures (RIs)** are defined using the European Commission's definition as “facilities that provide resources and services for research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields”. This includes major scientific equipment or sets of instruments, collections, repositories, archives or scientific data, computing systems, and communication networks.

The strategic importance of RIs is strongly supported by the **ERA Policy Agenda**, in synergy with the European Higher Education Area policy. In particular, **ERA action n. 8** is aimed at strengthening the sustainability, accessibility, and resilience of research infrastructures in the ERA, and highlights emerging challenges: sustainable funding to maintain excellence and competitiveness; equal opportunities to access the services provided by research infrastructures; the need to increase their social and economic impact; the need to focus on specific scientific issues and political challenges.

More in general, the European policies recognize the essential role of research infrastructures in **supporting fundamental and applied research** and tackling pressing social, health, economic and environmental challenges (see also Brno Declaration, 2022) and call for an enhanced accessibility, interoperability, and integration of the European research infrastructures ecosystem, also in the context of the digital transition. The Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe calls for further development of the open access to and better connection of new and existing European and national RIs in all fields of science and acknowledges their potential “in forming partnerships and pooling resources and connection to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)”.

The Council conclusions on Research Infrastructures (2 December 2022) acknowledge the need to further strengthen RIs and facilitate broader access to them, since they can greatly contribute to the competitiveness of the European economy. The Council conclusions also underline the “importance of the professional training of the staff in charge of RIs for the development of its knowledge and competences” Moreover, the Council emphasize “the critical role of RIs in producing, collecting, processing, storing and providing quality certified scientific data in accordance with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) principles, thus facilitating the use of such data across a broad range of disciplinary domains and internationally, and fundamentally contributing to the implementation of EOSC and open science policy”. **Open access policies of RIs** are also recognised as a major driver for knowledge circulation, inter-sectorial, and international mobility, promoting **specialised training** to researchers, students, managers, technicians and innovators.

Indeed, enhancing the integration and cross-border collaboration of the European RIs ecosystems implies the promotion and adoption of **open science principles** articulated in the **ERA action n.1**, aimed to “enable the open sharing of knowledge and the re-use of research outputs including through the development of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)”. As also underlined by the Research Data Alliance (“Open Science Monitor Case Study”), open sharing and exchange of research data and accessibility of metadata creates opportunities for re-use, and increases collaboration and transparent research practices. Not only the cooperation of researchers is required, but also the “adoption of social, organisational, and technical infrastructure solutions needed to reduce barriers to data sharing”.

In this context, Una Europa universities have undertaken, with the Una.Resin project, the first steps towards opening up and sharing their RIs and research data. The success in this endeavour requires first of all to acknowledge that **RIs in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) have unique characteristics**.

An important significant factor to consider is the **variety of RIs management models**: research infrastructures, like laboratories, can be managed by units or Core Facilities or as part of international projects. Moreover, as shown by Una.Resin benchmarking analysis (see Deliverable D2.1 “Mapping RIRs and priorities for joint strategy”), Una Europa universities host a vast range of infrastructures, **from small-medium individual RIs to large-scale ESFRI-oriented infrastructures and initiatives**. Small and medium-sized RIs of universities are usually strongly embedded and well-integrated in the local ecosystems, and engage stakeholders and users across all disciplinary fields and across sectors, including non-academic actors and citizens. Moreover, it is important to acknowledge that there are interconnections between small-medium sized RIs and ESFRI initiatives: creating or reinforcing the links between different categories of RIs (small, medium, large) can open new routes of collaboration, facilitate knowledge transfer, and enhance universities’ competitiveness at a European and international scale. The interplay between the European, national, and regional frameworks in relation to RIs is another crucial aspect: in particular, the alignment between ESFRI, national and regional roadmaps on RIs - which is different from one country to another - can significantly impact funding strategies and RIs’ long-term sustainability, thus affecting the further development and sharing of RIs in the Una Europa context.

Furthermore, as shown by a thorough survey on Open Research in Una Europa universities that was carried out within Una Resin, a crucial role in universities is played by **data infrastructures** - defined as “ICT infrastructures enabling services for supporting the data life-cycle” ([EOSC Glossary](#)) - in particular, **publication portals and institutional repositories**, as well as **tools for data transfer and statistics**, usually centrally managed by universities and available for all researchers.

WP2 of Una.Resin has analysed and discussed with stakeholders - major legal, financial, organisation, technical, and cultural **barriers** that still prevent sharing of RIs and data across institutions. But, considering the scale and complexity of the RIs landscape at the Alliance level,

a thorough understanding requires **further in-depth analysis both at institutional and theme-specific levels**. Devising and implementing possible ways to overcome these barriers requires a broad engagement of the academic and professional communities, and can help create meaningful links and collaboration with the stakeholders of the local ecosystem, including non-academic public and private actors as well as the civil society.

Important **enablers** have also been identified by Una.Resin, such as best practices in management models (e.g., Core Facilities) and the role of Open Science, which is promoted and put into practice by all Una Europa institutions through specific strategies, policies, guidelines or recommendations, together with dedicated tools. For example, it is worth mentioning that the University of Helsinki (UH) recognises **openness and accessibility** as central criteria for defining RIs and clearly highlights the significance of infrastructures in the context of HEIs: “Research infrastructures are prerequisite for conducting research. They support organised research and doctoral education as well as maintain and develop the capacity for research”. More in general, Una Europa universities are fully aligned with the aim of **ERA action n. 1** and embrace EOSC’s three main objectives:

1. Open science practices and skills are rewarded and taught;
2. Standards, tools and services allow researchers to find, access, re-use and combine results;
3. Sustainable and federated infrastructures enable open sharing of scientific results.

However, the Una.Resin Open Research Survey (cf. Section 2, Annex 2.2) has revealed existing barriers, such as lack of incentives, rewards and skills, low level of awareness and compliance with FAIR principles, and lack of integration and collaboration between discipline-specific research infrastructures. Research communities from all scientific fields - including researchers and research professionals – are encouraged to proactively engage in the discussion surrounding research data management and FAIR principles, taking full account of cross-domain and domain-specific standards towards the interoperability of research data infrastructures. Digital outputs (e.g., data, software, codes etc.) produced by research infrastructures need to be made open, better managed and reusable to stimulate research collaboration - also considering that funding bodies are increasingly embracing Open Science principles and expect researchers to comply with them.

The work done so far has also revealed the **richness of knowledge and expertise available within Una Europa universities** and has shown that improving the skills of RIs managers and data experts could be a crucial enabler for achieving a more open and shared ecosystem of infrastructures. WP2 has mapped, analysed and discussed the needs related to upskilling of RIs managers and data experts, considering the diversity of profiles and the constantly evolving skills required for the management of RIs and also taking into account that data infrastructures are often centrally supported. In this regard, Una Europa is fully aligned with **ERA action n.17** that targets all types of research managers - including data stewards and specialised research infrastructures professionals - and is aimed to “develop better R&I management capacity and

guidance for researchers and innovators across the entire ERA including laggard regions and research organisations, as well as pave the way towards institutional acknowledgement of the R&I management profession.”

To conclude, the strategic priorities proposed in this document, that are solidly grounded in the results of Una.Resin WP2 activities, are fully aligned with (and contributing to) the European policy priorities for RIs and data infrastructures.

Alignment with Una Europa strategies

The ERA Policy Agenda **action n.13** “Empower higher education institutions to develop in line with the ERA, and in synergy with the European Education Area” aims to support universities “in their efforts to transform and drive the ongoing green and digital transitions”. This ambition will be achieved through the development of enhanced goals and vision of the individual universities to “take transnational cooperation in education, R&I to a new level of intensity and scope and to develop a genuinely European dimension in higher education”. Two concrete European Initiatives, namely, the European Excellence Initiative (EEI) and European Universities Initiative (EUI), support this endeavor. These initiatives are fundamental in supporting the internationalisation of higher education in Europe to raise excellence in science and in knowledge valorisation of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) through **transnational cooperation**, e.g., on high quality short- and long-term mobility, co-creation of curriculum and collaboration on summer and winter schools, and raising awareness on recruitment and assessment issues.

Una Europa is centrally placed in the framework of the European Universities initiative. The **Una Europa 2030 Strategy** guides our collective actions by setting the Alliance’s vision for the current decade and articulating institutional and thematic priorities to ensure collaboration beyond the life cycle of individual projects in the coming decades. **Six individual thematic strategies** contribute to the overall Una Europa vision: (i) Teaching & Learning; (ii) Mobility; (iii) Research and Innovation (R&I); (iv) International dimension, (v) Sustainability and climate protection; (vi) Diversity and Inclusion.

WP1 of Una.Resin developed the **Una Europa Research & Innovation Strategy** (Deliverable 1.2) setting areas of actions that will drive the creation of a shared research and innovation ecosystem of collaborative and interdisciplinary research by 2030:

- **Strengthening the Una Europa Focus Areas**
 - Interdisciplinary Hubs
 - Training Researchers of the Future
 - Strengthening Collaboration with Non-academic Actors for Mutual Benefit
- **Engaging Researchers Broadly**
 - Supporting Bottom-Up Initiatives

- Promoting Mobility & Community Building
- Digitalising Collaboration
- **Opening up Research and Data Infrastructures**
 - Promoting openness of RIs and data infrastructures to foster research collaboration
 - Strengthening Research and Data Infrastructure Skills
 - Developing a stronger and more integrated Una Europa Research Infrastructure Ecosystem

Each area of activity embraces crosscutting values that shape the Una Europa research approach and align with the institutional priorities outlined in the 2030 Strategy. These values include diversity and human dignity, academic freedom, open research, individual well-being, environmental sustainability, organisational resilience, and global engagement.

Within the R&I Strategy (D1.2), the priority “Opening up Research and Data Infrastructures” gives a brief overview of the three strategic pillars of the **Una Europa Strategy and Action Plan for Sharing Research Infrastructures and Resources** that is thoroughly described in this document. A draft version of the R&I Strategy was discussed with the Board of Directors and Research Strategy Group of Una Europa (29th of March): based on the outcomes of this discussion and based on the consultations with relevant stakeholders including SSCs, Cluster experts and WPs members, the semi-final version of this document was prepared and all the Una.Resin deliverables were signed off during the joint meeting of BoD and RSG that took place on the 7th of June 2023 in Leiden.

The **first section** of this document describes in-depth the three pillars, presenting the specific objectives and actions, based on the needs identified through the Una.Resin WP2 activities such as benchmarking, consultations and workshops with stakeholders, and surveys by experts. For all the proposed actions, three levels of ambitions (low, medium, high) are identified corresponding to different timescales (from short to long-term) and requiring different levels of financial and human resources.

The **second section** includes, as Annexes, the reports of all the Una.Resin WP2 activities that led to the identification of challenges, needs, insights, and inputs laying the basis for the development of the strategy and action plan for opening up and sharing RIs. In particular, this section includes the following annexes: (i) report of the co-creation workshop with RIs stakeholders in the field of Cultural Heritage and One Health; (ii) main findings from the Open Research Survey and list of webinars organised by the Open Research Cluster; (iii) report highlighting the key takeaway messages of the joint workshop between Una.Resin and the RiTrainPlus project; (iv) format, concept, evaluation methodology, and preliminary results of the pilot actions.

1.1 Pillar 1: Promoting openness of RIs and data infrastructures to foster research collaboration

1.1.1 Identified needs

This sub-section will firstly describe the challenges identified from our previous mapping exercise on RIs. The results of the work carried out by WP2 of Una.Resin are related to barriers and enablers to opening and sharing research and data infrastructures and form the basis of the actions articulated in this first pillar. This previous work consists of the benchmarking report (D2.1 “Mapping RIRs and priorities for joint strategy”), the thematic mapping of RIs, the co-creation workshop report, and the pilot actions carried out in WP2. In view of creating the R&I ecosystem across Una institutions, the actions we are focusing on in this pillar to promote the openness and sharing of RIs, are the following:

- (1) Conduct an in-depth analysis on general and theme-specific barriers and enablers to sharing & opening RIs
- (2) Creating a RIs community
- (3) Creating a Data community
- (4) Development of tools to share information and knowledge related to RIs

Identified barriers

Our mapping exercise from the aforementioned D2.1 identified several barriers related to the opening and sharing of RIs to internal and external users that could hamper collaboration of researchers within universities and also with other Una Europa universities. Main barriers include: lack of qualified staff, registration constraints, bureaucracy, mobility, limited financial resources, as well as the need for additional clearance of ethical and privacy rights especially in relation to data in the health domains.

On the basis of the Open Research Survey report (2023), additional underlying barriers in relation to centrally managed RIs are linked to the difficulties in sharing infrastructure for publication and data infrastructure including tools and facilities. These difficulties are mainly related to organisational aspects including human and financial resource commitments, different management models for service provisions and institutional repositories, as well as legal and financial aspects. As regards the latter, institutions currently have very different models of financial support for open-access publications resulting in different support to researchers and students.

In addition, a specific aspect on barriers related to Open Data includes the limited access or sharing capacities because of standards, interoperability, and/or data storage and data protection and servers' security limitations.

Need for creating communities of research infrastructures

During the co-creation workshop, the researchers and RIs managers/experts showed great interest to get to know each other. The pilot matchmaking exercise among RIs within the thematic fields Cultural Heritage and One Health were therefore aimed to develop collaboration formats targeted to the academic and professional communities from these two thematic fields. The proposed format brought together academics and technicians of Una Europa RIs to discuss possible paths for sharing infrastructures. The specific scopes of the pilot actions (Genomics for One Health and University Museums and Digital collections for Cultural Heritage) were defined on the basis of discussion with RI Cluster members, SSCs, and the WP2 team.

During the workshops, the participants presented their infrastructures and available expertise and discussed their mutual interests; they also started a discussion on how to move concretely towards opening/sharing infrastructures and how to foster collaboration within the RIs network. Museums and digital collections representatives specifically discussed their interests in relation to actions proposed by the SSC Cultural Heritage. Genomics infrastructures representatives discussed their interests for possible collaborative activities related to the strategic priorities on RIs proposed by WP2, emphasising the importance of having a more in-depth understanding of the expertise and strengths of each institution.

The ideas that emerged in these workshops reveal the potential benefits of this format, e.g., the possibility to organise webinars or training courses on relevant topics, to increase the visibility of RIs and expertise available in each university through Una Europa website, to explore training opportunities for PhDs and early-stage researchers based on mobility, and to collaborate to the organisation of joint events or to undertake joint projects (e.g. the Virtual Museum of Una Europa universities heritage).

Need for creating a data community for data experts and managers

The Open Research Survey report signals ample opportunities to collaborate and exchange best practices on opening and sharing institutional infrastructures related to publications and research data, as well as on the external use of these infrastructures. The report also describes the need to identify and distinguish the target groups for training modules for the adoption, implementation, and enhancement of Open Research practices in each institution. In other words, a much more tailored approach can be developed according to the professional categories and their needs related to open research activities.

Not only the exchange of knowledge and best practices on sharing data is paramount, but also a common reflection on the following topics would greatly benefit partner universities: sustainability of disciplinary Open Research repositories; possible services and infrastructures for a multi-disciplinary research community; and the interoperability of data infrastructures (e.g., through metadata and harvesting systems, or tools) to stimulate interdisciplinary collaborative research. Collaboration at the Alliance level would also be key to addressing issues related to data sharing technologies as well as legal and ethical barriers.

In this process, the alignment with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is acknowledged as very important. Considering the work development of EOSC, how to concretely align as Una Europa with general principles and recommendations developed by EOSC, needs to be further analysed and explored at the Alliance level (cf. Section 2, Annex 2.2).

Universities are **service providers** of the EOSC and also **users** of the EOSC services: these two perspectives make it possible for the Alliance to effectively contribute to EOSC. This means that through Una Europa it is possible to clearly identify the common challenges of FAIR data principles and highlight the needs of researchers and research professionals and promote them. Moreover, the universities of the Alliance can address common barriers and increase awareness of FAIR principles in relation to educational and research activities, and this will benefit not only the academic community but also society at large.

The main players and target audience of these actions will be the community of data experts and managers, including those working at the level of research groups as well as professionals working on research data management in the central offices of universities, (i.e., the community implementing and promoting FAIR data principles, and gathering the needs and perspectives of researchers and research professionals).

Need for the development of tools to share information and knowledge on RIs

During the workshops and discussions with SSCs, researchers, RI managers and experts, it was mentioned several times that a prerequisite to collaborate on RIs, is to get to know the available infrastructures in the other Una Europa universities. Una Europa Institutions are very large, comprehensive universities, and this makes it difficult to have a complete overview of infrastructures and expertise.

Given this challenge, the development of a blueprint of a common digital catalogue of RIs was initiated in a pilot study to describe the process to harvest the existing information on Una Europa RIs via repositories, with the final aim to display the available RIs (and by extension along with services) in a common web portal. For the universities that have not (yet) developed an institutional catalogue of RIs, the blueprint will provide guidelines and indications on how to create one that eventually connects with the other institutional repositories.

The blueprint developed within the Una.Resin project (cf. Section 2, Annex 2.4) include the following contents: (i) Catalogues of infrastructures available in the Una Europa universities; (ii) Best practices; (iii) Lessons learned from the prototype that was created to show the potentialities of a common catalogue; (iv) Recommendations for a future shared catalogue (architecture, system, taxonomy); (v) Guidelines to develop a new catalogue of infrastructures at institutional level; (vi) Future improvement: a service portal for Una Europa infrastructures; (vii) Next steps.

An advanced version of this blueprint will be produced, so as to concretely progress towards the creation of the common RIs catalogue and a prospective portal of services.

1.1.2 Specific objectives and actions of Pillar 1

In response to the identified needs and challenges discussed above and based on Una.Resin WP2 outputs, the first pillar of the RI strategy is oriented towards promoting the openness of research and data infrastructures in our RI ecosystem to foster research collaboration across institutions. This means that the activities proposed under this pillar require the engagement of the research and data infrastructure communities in each institution. In the proposed actions, different levels of activities (low, medium and high) are distinguished, which correspond to the levels of ambition and available funding resources, including internal and external resources. In general, these different levels also correspond to the **time frame: short, medium and long-term** illustrating the possible pathways to the final objectives. Multiple actors of the RIs ecosystem are considered as beneficiaries and target audience: researchers, data scientists, software engineers, RI support managers, RI experts, RI trainers/educators, data stewards, data curators, policy makers, students and citizens.

Taking forward the in-depth analysis of barriers and enablers to opening and sharing research and data infrastructures

On the basis of the identified needs (discussed in 1.1.1), the first action aims to continue the in-depth analysis - already undertaken within Una.Resin - of institutional and theme-specific barriers that hinder the opening up of research and data infrastructures.

The first level of activities which include the **in-depth analysis of barriers in pilot thematic areas**, based on six drivers: (i) human/financial resource commitment; (ii) management models for services and repositories; (iii) legal issues; (iv) domain specific technical issues; (v) differences due to the national/regional context; (vi) business/cost models.

Special attention will be given to the sixth point on **business/cost models** since the long-term sustainability of RIs is highly dependent on accurate and auditable cost and business models of (core) facilities.

The medium-level activities will then focus on **identifying common enablers and solutions** for opening and sharing RIs, and formulating recommendations for key common principles that could form the basis for an Una Europa Charter for RIs (cf. link with action on Una Europa Charter for RIs proposed under Pillar 3). Good practices that are present at institutional level, or at regional/national level, could be considered in this process. Depending on the models adopted for sharing or opening RIs, institutional agreements might be required; in this context, it will be necessary to develop accurate costing models, including the assessment of costs required in providing trans-national and virtual access to RIs.²

² See [ESFRI “Guidelines on cost estimation for research infrastructures”](#) and the “Decision authorising the use of unit costs for the costs of providing trans-national and virtual access in Research Infrastructures actions under the Horizon Europe Programme (2021-2027)”

The most ambitious level of activities aims to **scale up the analysis** of barriers and enablers, and related actions, to other focus areas, and to create synergies with other Alliances on how to overcome barriers to opening and sharing RIs; these synergies will also be the basis for common advocacy actions towards the EC foreseen in Pillar 3.

Towards creating a RIs community

On the basis of the need arising from the research infrastructure stakeholders, this activity envisages **building a RIs community through networking and matchmaking activities targeted to RIs in specific thematic fields**. The themes addressed by the pilot actions of Una.Resin were “Museums and digital collections” and “Genomics”, but the methodology can be scaled and applied to other fields.

The ultimate objective of this activity is the creation of RIs’ theme-specific communities, that can exchange knowledge, discuss possible paths towards opening and sharing RIs, and undertake collaborations in research and education by, for example, exploring opportunities for training, promoting the mobility of researchers and staff, and developing joint funding proposals. The communities will **contribute to the strategies and action plans of the Self-Steering Committees** of the Una Europa: in this perspective, both research and educational activities of Focus Areas will be supported and enhanced by the collaboration between RIs across the Alliance.

These communities of RIs could be created, in the medium term, in different thematic fields and be further developed through the creation of **virtual thematic networks of RIs** that could also benefit from **communication and visibility** opportunities at the Alliance level (e.g., Una Europa website and newsletter). Physical mobility of researchers and research managers involved in these networks for **in-person visits, training seminars, workshops, and events** will contribute to consolidating the Una Europa RIs community, that could also be strengthened through the obtainment of competitive external funding. Further synergies could be sought in the long run with similar communities in other alliances.

The main **benefits** of these actions are the following:

- to stimulate community building and networking among the Una Europa RIs;
- to exchange practices and knowledge, promote mobility and training;
- to foster collaborations in research and education;
- to enhance RIs visibility within the Alliance as well as towards external actors and potential users.

Towards creating a Data community

On the basis of the need arising from the research and data infrastructure communities, we envisage a separate activity dedicated to the creation of a community of data managers/experts. Considering that specific knowledge on the digital and technical components

is required, broader activities are envisaged here. The focus on data infrastructure is at the research group level (theme-specific) referring to digital products including research data, metadata, software etc.; at the same time, the overall data management at the central institutional level implemented by institution-wide data support services needs to be involved. Depending on the target activity (i.e., research collaboration at RIs level vs. data management at the institutional level), the operationalisation of **FAIR data principles** needs to be agreed and consolidated according to specific circumstances.

The creation of a Data community will consider these specific levels and will bring together data managers and data experts to: (i) **promote best practices sharing** on key issues such as sustainability of data repositories and services, interoperability of data infrastructures and technologies, as well as legal and ethical barriers to data sharing; (ii) **promote the consolidation of FAIR principles** (in compliance with the EOSC recommendations). Physical mobility of experts and the creation of specific working groups will be key to scaling this action and consolidating a community that, in the long run, can create meaningful **synergies with open data networks in other Alliances** and contribute to relevant initiatives at the European and international level.

Creating a community of data experts and data managers is indeed **a crucial undertaking for the Alliance**, and also a necessary step to move towards opening and sharing research and data infrastructures to foster collaborative research. Moreover, by building a community of data experts/managers across its universities and by creating synergies with relevant initiatives on open data, Una Europa can play a very important and **strategic role for the development of the EOSC ecosystem**.

The main **benefits** of these actions are the following:

- Co-develop guidelines and principles on consolidation of FAIR principles.
- Upgrade and streamline existing data sources and generate data in order to stimulate effective transnational cooperation.
- Exchange knowledge and create synergies on existing data tools and technologies.
- Upgrade institutional capacities to update technologies and platforms to prepare for digital transition.
- Support institutions to develop digital skills for education and research purposes targeted towards students, research professionals and researchers.

Developing tools to share information and knowledge related to RIs

The proposed action is about the creation of a **Una Europa common digital catalogue of RIs** that will serve as a **unified access point for information on Una Europa RIs** to stimulate information sharing and ease cross-institutional access, with a view to fostering research collaboration. In the short term, an advanced version of the blueprint produced within Una.Resin WP2 could be co-developed to identify the concrete steps towards the creation of a common digital catalogue of RIs. In the medium-term, the activity aims to the actual creation of the digital

catalogue. The long-term envisaged output is the production of **common portal** disseminating all RIs available (including small and medium-sized RIs) as well as services and research outputs produced by the RIs.

The main **benefits** of this action are the following:

- increase awareness for the academic community about the RIs available across the Una Europa universities and facilitate access to them;
- promote R&I cooperation and an efficient use of RIs;
- connect RIs sharing and promote Open Science principles in their operation and activities;
- promote the RIs towards possible non-academic public, private and third sector users and also towards citizens.

1.1.3 Proposed action plan

Action 1: Conduct an in-depth analysis on institutional and theme-specific barriers and enablers in sharing & opening RIs

Level of ambition	Low	Medium	High
	Identification and further analysis of institutional and theme-specific barriers in pilot thematic areas on the following drivers (non-exhaustive list): <ol style="list-style-type: none"> human/financial resource commitment, management models for services and repositories, legal issues domain specific technical issues differences due to the national/regional context business-cost models 	Based on the identified barriers, identification of common enablers and solutions (e.g., most effective management models, costing models, etc.), and recommendations of common principles that can serve as a basis for the Una Europa Charter for RIs (see on this point Pillar 3 - Action 1)	Scale theme-specific analysis and related actions to other focus areas

	Create synergies between stakeholders and experts (RIs managers, legal experts, researchers etc.) at the institutional level to analyse barriers	Create synergies across institutions and analyse best practices at institutional and regional/national levels	Create synergies to share and overcome the identified barriers with other European university alliances (relation to Pillar 3)
Actors	RI managers, researchers, experts from central legal, financial, RI departments, data scientist, IT-engineer, data stewards, data curators	RI managers, researchers, experts from central legal, financial, RI departments, data scientist, IT-engineer, data stewards, data curators	RI managers, researchers, policy makers, legal experts, European Universities Alliances
Beneficiaries	RI managers, researchers (Self-Steering Committees), teaching staff, students (as beneficiaries of courses that could make use of the results of this action).	RI managers, researchers (Self-Steering Committees), teaching staff, students (as beneficiaries of courses that could make use of the results of this action).	RI managers, researchers (Self-Steering Committees), teaching staff, students, policymakers, other Alliances and other universities that could uptake the results of this action

Overall requirement for Action 1 (and related risk): commitment of university policy makers to work towards opening and sharing research and data infrastructure, which is one of the priorities in the Una.Resin R&I strategy. The main risk is not only the lack of institutional commitment but also the lack of incentives for professionals and academics to work on the tasks foreseen by the action.

Action 2: Creating a RIs community

Level of ambition	Low	Medium	High
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	<p>Organisation of theme-specific matchmaking workshops and events for RIs (e.g., genomics, museums, digital technologies, mass spectrometry, etc.) to identify common interests and paths towards sharing</p> <p>Create synergies and foster collaboration in theme-specific groups of RIs</p>	<p>Application/scaling of the matchmaking formats to other focus areas</p> <p>Create virtual thematic networks of infrastructures across the Alliance, and give them visibility (e.g., through Una Europa website)</p> <p>In-person seminars, workshops and events of thematic RIs networks</p> <p>Stimulate interest of researchers/RI managers to apply for common funding proposals for infrastructure or other research initiatives</p>	<p>Creation of synergies with other European universities alliances on specific thematic areas</p>
Actors	RI managers and experts, researchers (Self-Steering Committees)	RI managers and expert, researchers (Self-Steering Committees)	Policy makers, European Universities Alliances, researchers (Self-Steering Committees)
Beneficiaries	Researchers, RI managers, teaching staff, students	Researchers, RI managers, teaching staff, students	European Universities Alliances, researchers and teaching staff, students, citizens, other universities

Overall requirement for Action 2 (and related risk): A dedicated EC funding call on interconnecting RIs (network creation) would be needed to stimulate networking and community-building activities, while the risk is that the lack of funding will not allow to make these activities systematic and sustainable.

Action 3: Creating a Data community

Level of ambition	Low	Medium	High
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	<p>Promoting best practices sharing on key issues (e.g., sustainability of data repositories and services; interoperability of data infrastructures and technologies; legal and ethical barriers to data sharing)</p> <p>Promoting the consolidation³ of FAIR principles (in compliance with the EOSC recommendations)</p>	<p>Promote physical mobility (link to Pillar 2) to consolidate the community</p> <p>Monitor the FAIRness of the Alliance members, through the use of e.g., <u>OpenAIRE - Connect</u> as a single entry-point to all research outputs of the members</p> <p>Stimulate interest towards applying for common funding for Open Data initiatives</p> <p>Set up a working group at Una Europa level to explore the possibility to offer services on open data</p>	<p>Creation of synergies between Open Data networks across European university alliances (link to Pillar 2 and 3) and contribution to initiatives on open data at European level</p>
Actors	Data scientists, engineers, data stewards, data curators, SSC on Data and AI	Data scientists, engineers, data stewards, data curators, SSC on Data and AI, funding officers	Policy makers, European Universities Alliances
Beneficiaries	Broader audience involved in research data management, academic communities	Broader audience involved in research data management, academic communities	Broader audience involved in research data management, academic communities of other Alliances, other universities

Overall requirement for Action 3 (and related risk): A dedicated EC funding call aimed at the creation of network of data experts would be needed to stimulate networking and community-

³ There are number of activities which are oriented towards the consolidation of FAIR principles (read-write capability & managed accessibility), regulation through policies, promotion of implementation on guidelines and frameworks to set flows and models, and organisation of thematic services. EOSC foundations call for: i. persistent identifiers (a mechanism for naming and location documents, data and software in a persistent manner); ii. metadata and ontologies: a mechanism for discovery of and access to documents, data and software in a structured manner; iii. internet identity: an Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) (EC 2021).

building activities, while the risk is that the lack of funding will not allow to make these activities systematic and sustainable. In addition, depending on the barriers analysed in Action 1, working activities oriented towards open data are closely related to the research domain (cf. Deliverable 2.1 on the thematic mapping of RIs in relation to the assessment of FAIR data principles).

Action 4: Development of tools to share information and knowledge related to RIs

Level of ambition	Low	Medium	High
	Creation of an advanced blueprint including technical solutions and steps for the development of a common digital catalogue of RIs	Development of a common RIs digital catalogue	Development of a common portal including RIs and services
Actors	IT experts, RIs experts	RIs experts, RIs departments, IT experts, IT departments, data managers, data stewards, policy makers	RIs experts, RIs departments, IT experts, IT departments, data managers, data stewards, policy makers
Beneficiaries	Researchers, RI managers, funding officers	Researchers, teaching staff, students, RI managers, funding officers, external users (academic and non-academic), citizens, other European university alliances	Internal and external researchers, students, RI managers, funding and policy officers, external non-academic users, citizens, other European university alliances

Overall requirement on Action 4 (and related risk): Institutional commitment of Una Europa universities to undertake the concrete steps (including investment of resources) needed to achieve the creation of a common catalogue of RIs and a portal of services.

1.1.4 Resources

The implementation of the 4 actions suggested above requires institutional commitment from the governance of each university in terms of human resources (Cluster members and additional effort of other professionals) and financial resources. Action 2, concerning RIs

community building based on networking/matchmaking, at its low level of ambition may align with the activities of SSCs proposed under Una Futura. Further, all actions which require engagement, coordination and connection through mobility, as foreseen at the medium and high-level of ambitions, will require dedicated funding to develop and implement the proposed activities. In other words, the proposed activities require structured funding dedicated to the development of communities and to support their activities, e.g., through funds for mobility. Self-evidently, the proposed activities under Pillar 1 are closely related to the activities described in Pillars 2 and 3.

1.2 Pillar 2: Strengthening Research and Data Infrastructure Skills

1.2.1 Identified needs

Need to strengthen the skills of RIs managers and data experts

The need to strengthen skills and exchange knowledge related to RIs' management strongly emerged from the benchmarking analysis and thematic mapping of RIs (see D2.1 "Mapping RIRs and priorities for joint strategy"). The need for **skilled staff managing research infrastructures** has been identified as a priority that the Alliance needs to address to move towards an ecosystem where RIs and RIs services are shared. Upskilling personnel involved in the management of RIs, by addressing the **evolving skills required to manage RIs**, is in fact a prerequisite to ease the opening and sharing of RIs at the Una Europa level and beyond.

The benchmarking mapping highlighted that managing RIs according to similar principles is a prerequisite to ease their opening and sharing at the Una Europa level and beyond and that the lack of resources and training for specialised staff to lead and to run infrastructures (both from the administrative and technical point of view) is a major bottleneck. The thematic mapping of the RIs in the field of One Health and Cultural Heritage also confirmed that the lack of resources and training for specialized staff is a major obstacle that could hamper collaboration with other universities. Retention of skills and expertise of the personnel managing RIs is a key issue, since RIs "sustainability also depends on the **expertise and career perspectives of specialised staff running the research facilities**" (LERU 2017 paper *Four Golden Principles for Enhancing the Quality, Access and Impact of Research Infrastructures*).

Which skills and knowledge related to RIs management should be strengthened to enable the sharing of RIs and which initiatives could be undertaken at the Alliance level was one of the topics discussed during the breakout room discussion of the co-creation workshop with stakeholders that was held in June 2022 (see Section 2, Annex 2.1 "Report on the co-creation workshop). Participants emphasized the **diversity of professional profiles** - also considering different national contexts - and the **variety of skills** related to RIs management such as management skills (including administration and finance, law and safety), digital competencies,

interdisciplinary knowledge as well as horizontal skills related to communication and dissemination. Some of the training needs identified were related to the specific thematic fields of Cultural Heritage and One Health, but also transversal needs for competency development of RIs managers. The importance of physical mobility and staff exchange (including for administrative staff and technicians) as crucial drivers for mutual learning and training, was strongly underlined during the discussion.

Need to share good practices

Una.Resin surveys, benchmarking exercises and discussions with researchers and experts during workshops and pilot actions clearly demonstrated that there is a substantial amount of **knowledge and expertise available in Una Europa universities** on good governance of RIs and on key principles of Open research, such as research data management and data compliance, instrumentation and technical aspects, management of (core) facilities and RIs policies.

The need for an exchange of best practices or the setup of **mutual learning exercises** strongly emerged from the **Open Research Survey** (see Section 2, Annex 2.2) as well as in the framework of the **Open Research Cluster activities**. The Open Research survey highlighted the role of Open Science in promoting principles and activities that can **ease access to research publications, data and data infrastructures**; this affects the process of removing barriers and promotes a wider use of results by disseminating and communicating scientific knowledge to a wider public. Specific information was collected and processed on the areas where best practice sharing would be most beneficial, and the areas where input and contributions can be given by different institutions. For example, universities expressed the interest to know more about, for example, the following topics: the conditions and benefits of being an ORCID member; the functions, provisions, and workflows for institutional or disciplinary publication repositories; Open Access university presses; secure systems for sensitive data; software allowing collaboration on active data; software used for anonymising or pseudonymising data; conditions for sharing.

This is an initial list of topics that can be implemented in the form of mutual learning and training where institutional experts can offer and share their expertise to others and vice versa. The Open Research Survey (2023) shows that some expertise is available within Una institutions whereas some others are not. On the latter case, they will require to search networks/institutions that hold this expertise. Creating synergies with other Alliance projects in this case can be valuable.

It is important to underline that, in Una.Resin, the activities of the Open Research Cluster and of the Research Infrastructures Cluster have been strongly oriented towards mutual learning. For example, the Open Research Cluster organised a **series of webinars on Open Research**, which were of common interest, such as: how to provide open access without paying; data management plans; implementation of institutional research data repositories; digital

humanities, multilingual research and infrastructures, and the national open access repository (see the complete list in Section 2, Annex 2.2).

Now this exercise needs to be taken further, so as to **structure opportunities for knowledge exchange** across the Alliance and beyond. Sharing guidelines, models and tools among the RIs managers, research managers, data experts and researchers of Una Europa institutions could be promoted much more. This action requires setting up a working group of professionals to identify needs at the institutional level, define common areas of interest, and share the knowledge and practices across Una Europa institutions. Mutual learning can take several forms:

- Sharing best practices can take the form of joint activities and awareness raising campaigns (e.g., Una Europa Open Research Day or training modules for Una Europa summer schools, PhD programmes, Open Research Ambassadors/Champions etc.). They can focus on basic principles relating to Open Research, including citizen engagement (methodologies), and also create meaningful synergies with the joint BA programme on European Studies and the Una Europa micro-credentials formats.
- Mutual learning can also occur in digital formats making use of digital platform formats (e.g., webinars) where technical advice and documentation can be shared amongst research professionals.
- Physical mobility for researchers (cf. Pillar 1 – Action 2 on RIs community) and research management support staff could be envisaged to support mutual learning, to improve the skills of different target groups related to the 8 ambitions of the EU Open Science Policy.

The need for training programme The joint workshop with RiTrainPlus project held in October 2022 (see Section 2, Annex 2.3) highlighted the importance to collaborate to develop **training programme** to prepare future managers and operators of European RIs and Core Facilities and enable the continuing training of those who are already holding such positions in the field. This should be fulfilled by **introducing theoretical and practical training paths for managerial skills**, throughout the entire university career (Bachelor, Master and PhD) and at the executive level (targeting current medium and senior managers of RIs and Core Facilities).

It is important to underline that, considering the specific RIs ecosystem of universities, it is crucial to identify and address the training needs related to RIs and data infrastructures management taking into consideration also the **specificities of small and medium-sized RIs**, so that the entire RIs and data community of the Alliance will be able to benefit from these actions.

1.2.2 Specific objectives and actions of Pillar 2

The objective of this pillar is to strengthen the skills of research infrastructure and data managers by setting up mutual learning processes based on a peer learning approach and by addressing the training needs of current and future managers of infrastructures (also through synergies with the RiTrain Plus project) - so that the whole RIs and Data community of the Alliance can benefit from structured opportunities for upskilling and professional development.

Implementing mutual learning processes

Collaboration on research and data infrastructures relies on **highly-skilled managerial staff**. Taking into consideration the diversity of profiles and the wide range of **constantly evolving professional skills** relevant for managing RIs and data infrastructures (**including transversal skills**) and drawing on the richness and complementary strengths of its universities, Una Europa will promote mutual learning processes that will lead to an **increased capacity of managing research and data infrastructures**.

Mutual learning processes involving RIs and data managers will be based, first of all, on the exchange of knowledge and best practices on topics of common interest through digital means. In the medium term, Una Europa will support a systematic exchange of knowledge by building on existing formats and initiatives of **staff mobility and job shadowing** (e.g., Staff weeks, Live my life scheme). In particular, mobility of staff for **online and in-person exchange visits** will be a **crucial driver of mutual learning; internships and stage** at the research infrastructures of the Una Europa universities could also be promoted.

It is worth underlining that one of the major aims of the Una Futura project is to **empower professional staff** - including personnel involved in research support, RIs and research data management - by fostering mutual learning and training through mobility. The proposed action will lead, in the long term, to **structured exchange formats and programme**, as well as to the creation of synergies with other relevant initiatives and with other alliances. These activities will provide concrete opportunities of learning and professional development for RIs and data managers, thus strengthening the added value of being part of the Alliance.

It is crucial to recognize that **Clusters of experts** will be crucial to supporting mutual learning processes. In particular, Clusters of experts will identify specific topics where the exchange of best practices could be beneficial. For example, Core Facilities management has already emerged within Una.Resin as a topic of interest. As previously mentioned, within Una.Resin, the Open Research Cluster has organised a series of webinars on Open Science topics and institutional good practices. Moreover, the Open Research Survey Report represents a very useful starting point to organising the sharing of best practices in areas of mutual interest. In this regard, it is important to consider that RIs are a major driver for the promotion of Open Research and Open Research-related skills (e.g., open access publication, research data management, and research outputs resulting from open research activities). Opening and sharing RIs will be fostered by promoting **open research education**, also through **open**

educational resources (OER). Specific attention will be devoted to **FAIR data principles**: the community of data experts (cf. Pillar 1) will play a key role in this perspective.

Implementing training activities

Training activities will be promoted to address the needs related to the **management of RIs** (including small and medium-size RIs) and data infrastructures, thus addressing one of the major barriers towards sharing infrastructures.

Una Europa will continue to explore the **collaboration with the RiTrain Plus project**, that aims to design and implement an educational and training programme to fulfil the competency requirements for the current and future managers of European Research Infrastructures and Core Facilities. In addition, complementary actions and various synergies that will contribute to strengthening competencies for the management of research infrastructures, will be developed.

Una Europa has already started a preliminary discussion with RiTrainPlus and, as a first concrete step, will explore the possibility of certifying **micro-credentials** to the Learning Activities (focused on transversal topics and critical to the management of every research infrastructure) offered to **students at European Qualification Framework (EQF) 6, 7 and 8** and include them in the Longitudinal Learning Path developed within RiTrainPlus for the next Academic Year. In this regard, it is worth mentioning that Una Europa has already developed micro-credentials: a Microcredential programme on sustainability was developed by three universities of the Alliance.

Una Europa will also explore opportunities for developing complementary actions related to the training of research infrastructures managers and operators, since RiTrainPlus has also the aim to design and deliver **executive post-graduate courses**, specialised training courses and workshops to meet the needs for professional skills oriented towards the management of research infrastructure on issues such as governance, management, maintenance, organisation, financial, socio-economic impact analysis and internationalisation. More generally, the cooperation with RiTrainPlus will focus on creating synergies and added value for achieving the Una Europa long-term ambition of creating a seamless ecosystem of shared research infrastructures.

Considering the specific characteristics of the RIs ecosystem of universities, it is important to continue, in the short term, the **analysis of training needs** related to the management of small and medium-size RIs and data infrastructures, taking into account the specificities related to different thematic fields. In the medium term, it is paramount to engage the RIs and Data community (cf. Pillar 1) in the development of possible actions to address those needs, also by setting up specific working groups that could also promote joint applications for funding. In particular, funding calls related to the professional development of research managers could be a further opportunity to develop (or benefit from) networking and training programme aimed to improve the skills, career development, and professional development of RIs and data

managers. The Alliance may thus contribute to the ambitious long-term scenario of creating a European network for training RIs managers.

The long-term ambition of this action is to create an environment where **structured training opportunities** are co-created with and available for the Una Europa community of RIs and data managers. This will also benefit other European university alliances and other universities.

1.2.3 Proposed action plan

Action 1: Implementing mutual learning processes

Level of ambition	Low	Medium	High
Activities	<p>Exchange of knowledge and best practices involving RIs managers and data managers, through all digital means, including virtual meetings, webinars and specific online seminars on topics of common interest such as (non-exhaustive list):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - organisation of activities & RIs management models - RIs and facilities related practices, services, tools and technologies - communication & dissemination activities 	<p>Promote mobility of staff for job shadowing and in-person exchange visits (e.g., through the Live my life scheme and Staff week format)</p> <p>Creation of synergies across the Alliance by setting up of specific working groups on topics of common interest, also for promoting the development of joint proposal</p>	<p>Organisation and implementation of structured exchange formats and programme across the Alliance devoted to RIs and data managers</p> <p>Creation of synergies with other relevant initiatives and other Alliances, to broaden and strengthen mutual learning processes</p>
Actors	<p>Researchers; Teaching staff; RIs managers; Open Research experts; data managers</p>	<p>Researchers; Teaching staff; RIs managers; Open Research experts; data managers; funding officers</p>	<p>Researchers, RIs managers; Open Research experts; data managers; funding officers; Policy makers; European Universities Alliances</p>
Beneficiaries ⁴	<p>Researchers; RIs managers; Teaching staff; Open Research experts; data managers and broader audience involved in research data management</p>	<p>Researchers; RIs managers; Teaching staff; Open Research experts; data managers and broader audience involved in research data management; policy makers</p>	<p>Researchers; RIs managers; Teaching staff; Open Research experts; data managers and broader audience involved in research data management</p>

⁴ Here the actors and beneficiaries are similar groups. Teaching staff is included as indirect actor and beneficiary since outputs of this action can offer insights that could possibly be relevant in educational activities.

			Policy makers, other universities and European Universities Alliances
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Overall requirement for Action 1 (and related risk): Institutional commitment of Una Europa universities to implement systematic actions aimed at mutual learning and exchange of knowledge; the risk is that the lack of sustainable external funding for the Alliance will hamper the sustainability of these processes - in particular, undermining the possibility of setting structured exchange formats and programme.

Action 2: Implementing training activities

Level of ambition	Low	Medium	High
	<p>Explore opportunities for developing complementary actions with RiTrain Plus related to the training of managers and professionals of RIs and Core facilities</p> <p>Explore training needs of RIs and Data communities, considering the specificities of small-medium size RIs and of different thematic fields (link to Pillar 1)</p>	<p>Create a working group that will be in charge for implementing the complementary actions with RiTrain Plus identified in the first step</p> <p>Create working groups in the RIs and Data communities (link to Pillar 1) to develop actions to address the training needs of managers of RIs (including small-medium size) in different thematic fields and of data managers.</p> <p>Collaborate to the creation of a “European network for training RIs managers”, for example by developing (or participating in/benefitting from) project proposals that will contribute to this objective.</p>	<p>Develop and implement structured training modules and programme by/for the RIs and Data community (link to Pillar 1)</p>
Actors	Researchers and RIs managers, data managers,	Researchers and RIs managers, data managers, Open	Researchers and RIs managers, data managers, RitrainPlus

	Open Research experts, RitrainPlus team	Research experts Funding officers, RiTrain Plus team, Una Europa vzw	team; Una Europa vzw, Funding officers
Beneficiaries	Researchers and RIs managers, data managers, Open Research experts, teaching staff and students	Researchers and RIs managers, data managers and Open Research experts, teaching staff and students	Policy makers, Researchers and RIs managers, data managers and OR experts, teaching staff and students, other European Universities Alliances and other universities

Overall requirement for Action 2 (and related risk): Una Europa universities should commit to the long-term objective related to the training and professional development of RIs managers, by engaging in concrete actions, including the development of joint proposal to obtain dedicated funding; the risk is that the lack of funding will frustrate this ambition.

1.2.4 Resources

The mutual learning processes and the analysis of training needs (as well as the co-development of possible actions to address those needs) will be developed through the engagement of RIs and data experts/managers from the Alliance’s universities. This action, in the short term, will mainly rely on the effort of internal staff; in particular the Clusters of experts could coordinate the formats for exchanging knowledge and best practices. In the medium to long run, **sustainable funding for the Alliance** will be key to scale up these actions to the highest level of ambition.

The training and mutual learning through mobility of staff for exchange visits (organise online digital courses and in person visits) will build on existing formats and initiatives like Staff weeks and “Live my life” scheme; these activities will be carried out in close connection with the **Una Futura project (WP9 - Empowering staff)**. Una Europa universities will also explore the possibility to develop joint applications under the Erasmus+ and equivalent calls to support mobility actions.

The training programme to fulfil the competency requirements for the current and future managers of European Research Infrastructures and Core Facilities will be carried out in collaboration with the RiTrainPlus project. Una Europa universities will explore possible complementary actions and synergies with the RiTrainPlus; these actions could be implemented through working groups involving the interested universities.

Applications for external funding, in collaboration with RiTrainPlus, will be aimed at developing project proposals that will contribute to the creation of a “European network for training RIs

managers”. Una Europa universities will also explore opportunities related to the **funding calls on professional development of research managers** (e.g., under the “Research Infrastructures” and “Widening participation and Strengthening the ERA” pillars of the Horizon Europe programme jointly developing proposals or coordinating efforts to benefit from the results of approved projects. The Research Coordination Cluster could support this process.

1.3 Pillar 3: Developing a stronger and more integrated Una Europa Research Infrastructure Ecosystem

1.3.1 Identified needs

Need for common principles and policies towards sharing RIs

One of the key take-aways from the Una.Resin efforts to share and open RIs is that RIs collaboration can create ample opportunities for actual activities of Una Europa researchers. To unlock the potential of RIs in the implementation of cross-border and strategic research collaboration addressing major societal challenges, Una Europa universities must **promote and support their research infrastructures**, as well as formulate and adopt **policies and principles towards sharing them across the institutions and towards external actors** (including non-academic actors and citizens).

Sharing RIs across Una Europa universities requires two critical conditions. Firstly, the Alliance universities must make a coordinated effort to implement institutional strategies, policies and initiatives aimed at overcoming financial, organisational, technical and cultural barriers that are still hampering the possibility to share research infrastructures within and across institutions. Secondly, there must be a coordinated effort at the European level to improve policies and funding instruments for supporting and strengthening the RIs ecosystem of universities.

These needs have strongly emerged through various activities under the Una.Resin project. According to the D.2.1. benchmarking report, significant variations in policies and practices exist across Una Europa RIs, including differences in management structures. Although a no one-size-fits-all model of management is possible, especially taking into consideration the specificities of RIs (based, for example, on technologies), some basic principles can be identified and promoted. The report has highlighted the need for collaborative actions to connect infrastructures and improve their accessibility. For example, the standardisation of general guidelines and protocols for producing metadata could already simplify the implementation of technical and digital solutions aimed at creating a unified ecosystem.

The reports have also shed light on the fact that all RIs encounter multiple challenges in enhancing their capacities, including financial, cultural, and technical barriers. However, the similarities in the obstacles faced by the RIs of Una Europa may prompt the exploration of potential shared solutions (cf. analysis of barriers and enablers in Pillar 1). By leveraging the identified barriers and enablers from benchmarking and co-creation workshop reports of Una.Resin, members of the Alliance can exchange their best practices (cf. mutual learning processes in Pillar 2), make recommendations on possible **enablers for sharing** different types of RIs (cf. Pillar 1) and collaborate to formulate **common guiding principles** that can be adopted and promoted by the universities of the Alliance.

Need to improve the funding landscape for RIs

The in-depth analysis of the funding landscape carried out in the benchmarking analysis (2022) shows that a critical issue regarding costs is related to the fact that the whole lifecycle of RIs is only very rarely covered by available funds, especially for small and medium-size RIs. RIs funding is needed not only in the initial phases but also for upgrading and ensuring sustainability of high standard RIs: lack of long-term, high cost and structural recurrent funding for equipment and facilities is mentioned as a major problem for maintaining sustainable RIs.

The highly variable and competitive nature of funding sources available to develop RIs and cover related costs such as personnel, membership fees, maintenance and renewal, coupled to co-funding constraints, as well as upgrading technical areas oriented towards interoperability and interconnectivity, persistently threatens the **long-term sustainability of RIs**, and represents an important bottleneck. In particular, three main difficulties were identified: (i) the lack of dedicated long-term, recurring subsidies; (ii) the extreme fragmentation of funding mechanisms, in particular with regards to competitive-based programmes; (iii) the relative absence of funding for small and medium-sized RIs since most of the EU funds available to Una Europa institutions are being targeted towards larger scale infrastructures.

For these reasons, sharing RIs at national, European and international scales remains a real challenge for most Una Europa Universities. In Pillar 1 we propose concrete actions aimed to further analyse barriers to opening and sharing RIs, including financial challenges, and to identify common enablers and solutions to overcome them. But, as also recommended in WP2 benchmarking analysis (D2.1), in order to be able to share RIs at the Alliance level, it is crucial to strengthen the RIs ecosystem of universities by advocating for an improvement of funding calls and synergies of funds at European level oriented towards the interoperability and accessibility.

In this context, LERU (League of European Research Universities) recommendations on RIs sustainable funding and access are particularly meaningful and coherent with our analysis. Acknowledging the fact that funding for construction and especially maintenance and renewal of RIs is limited, the 2017 paper *Four Golden Principles for Enhancing the Quality, Access and Impact of Research Infrastructures*, LERU highlights the need to develop mechanisms “to make RIs robust and (self-) sustainable – a smart strategy for the RI to remain competitive in its field and to be leading and agile in technology developments supporting science. Elements of the sustainability strategy are first of all financial, including base funding for running costs, upgrading, and maintenance costs. RIs should also be able to **allocate resources to technological innovations, proof-of-principle and feasibility studies**, for which no regular funding is typically available. Sustainability also depends on the **expertise and career perspectives of specialised staff running the research facilities.**”

In the 2022 paper *Developing a strong, politically and societally relevant research infrastructure ecosystem in Europe*, LERU addresses the key issue of sustainable funding for existing and

new research infrastructures by proposing several actions, such as: working on how to combine different funding streams to help RIs line up funding from multiple sources; develop a map of funding opportunities for RIs to help them identify funding sources over their complete life cycle in order to develop a realistic and sustainable business model that takes into consideration different possible revenue streams; realign funding instruments for RIs to ensure that funding can be used for maintenance, renewal, and decommissioning, and not only on establishment; improve the funding for the accessibility and connectivity and interoperability of RIs (e.g., for remote access).

Starting from these recommendations, Una Europa can bring in the **specific perspective of a European University Alliance** working to overcome obstacles towards institutional transformation aimed at sharing RIs. Una Europa universities acknowledge the importance of working together, in close collaboration with Una Europa vzw, towards an improvement of the funding landscape for RIs, especially oriented to small and medium-scale RIs, with a view to strengthening the R&I ecosystem of the Alliance. In this context, **working together with other university alliances and in synergy/complementarity with other university networks** (e.g., The Guild and LERU) is extremely crucial to realise these ambitious objectives.

1.3.2 Specific objectives and actions of Pillar 3

This pillar aims at developing a stronger and more integrated Una Europa Research Infrastructures Ecosystem by promoting common visions and principles for sharing RIs across the Alliance and advocating, together with other European University Alliances and in synergy with other networks, for an improvement of the funding landscape for RIs, with specific attention to the challenges faced by smaller and medium-scale RIs in Higher Education Institutions.

Institutional policies and strategies towards sharing RIs across the Alliance and beyond

The objective of Una Europa is to fully realise the potential of collaborative research through the promotion of our distinctive assets and the establishment of policies and principles that encourage the sharing of our research infrastructures. This requires a coordinated effort to address financial, organisational, technical, legal and cultural barriers that restrict the sharing of research and data infrastructures within and across institutions.

Una Europa universities will commit to adopt a shared vision for the sharing and opening up of RIs. By consulting a wide range of stakeholders (see the list of specific actors and beneficiaries in the tables of the proposed action plan), Una Europa universities will continue to develop **policies** that improve access and connection across the RIs of the Alliance and will also encourage the adoption of **common principles** as a basis for developing a more open, inclusive, and interconnected Una Europa ecosystem of RIs and the extension of access to external users including non-academic actors, and citizens.

The most efficient and ambitious action would be to co-design and promote an **Una Europa Charter for Research Infrastructures**⁵ that will encourage the adoption of common general principles on the sharing RI as a **basis for developing the Una Europa ecosystem of RIs for Research, Innovation and Education**. This initiative will be based on the engagement of the RIs and Data community and will thus be closely aligned with Pillar 1, which focuses on promoting the openness of RIs and data infrastructures to facilitate collaboration. However, it will also emphasize the development of institutional frameworks and the engagement of high-level policy makers. By targeting both **grassroots efforts and top-down approaches**, Una Europa aims to drive meaningful change - including **cultural change** - towards a more open and collaborative research eco-system.

The Charter will include common principles for:

- openness of tools and data;
- long-term and sustainable managerial models and practices;
- principles and guidelines on accessibility, connectivity and interoperability;
- teaching and training activities;
- widening access to non-academic actors and citizens, taking into consideration existing models and best practices of collaboration and sharing of infrastructures in the local ecosystems.

In addition to stakeholder consultations with the internal actors, the Una Europa Charter for Research Infrastructures will be built upon the framework defined by the European Charter for Access to research infrastructures and the experience of its implementation.

As part of the Charter, Una Europa could produce a **checklist for RIs**, which would enable them to evaluate their organisational and data policies and practices and streamline their efforts to meet the guidelines set out in the Charter. In order to facilitate the sharing and opening up of RIs, it is important to include in the Charter consistent **safety policies**, which can be achieved through the establishment of user agreements for both internal and external use.

To promote these common principles, **awareness-raising actions** will be undertaken to drive a broader **cultural change** towards the sharing of RIs across the academic community and towards external non-academic actors, including citizens. To demonstrate the successful implementation of the common policies and principles outlined in the Una Europa Research Infrastructure Charter, Una Europa will leverage its flagship RIs as exemplars. These RIs will serve as showcases for the effective adoption and execution of the Charter's guidelines,

⁵ The idea to co-design a Una Europa Charter for Research Infrastructures has first emerged during the RIs benchmarking activities as part of a possible "Una RIs without Borders" Labelling Initiative.

providing valuable insights into best practices and offering practical examples for other RIs to follow.

Advocacy and lobbying actions at European level

Una Europa considers it crucial to strengthen and give more visibility to the RIs ecosystems of the universities, by advocating for policies and funding instruments that can support these ecosystems in terms of accessibility, openness, interconnection, and sustainability. In particular, “holistic” funding instruments are needed, i.e., funding the full lifecycle of RIs: renewal, expansion, openness, futureproofing. By **engaging in advocacy and lobbying efforts**, Una Europa aims to contribute to the **enhancement of funding instruments and policies for RIs at the European level**.

In this context, Una Europa will participate in the relevant internal and external stakeholders' consultations. While we will give special attention to consultations pertaining to RIs and their support, we will also seek out other avenues for advocating the enhancement of RIs support through discussions related to European Universities and the actions of the ERA Policy Agenda.

In particular, Una Europa will advocate for **funding instruments that can ensure the long-term sustainability of RIs, including small-medium scale RIs**. As emerged from the benchmarking analysis and mapping exercises, small and medium-sized RIs are confronted with specific challenges in terms of accessibility and long-term sustainability, e.g., they require maintenance, upgrading and managing RIs from a life cycle perspective. The absence of funding opportunities on the European level poses a major challenge for small and medium-sized RIs, which often play a critical role in maintaining their universities' research activities. This is primarily because most of the existing financial EU mechanisms prioritize the support of larger-scale RIs. Consequently, smaller RIs face significant challenges in obtaining the resources required to open and share their resources and services as they require additional efforts to the existing operation and at the same time find the need to integrate with the wider European research landscape. Addressing these challenges and creating synergies with ESFRI-level infrastructures and projects, as well as with national and regional roadmaps, is strategically important to empower the uniqueness and strengths of these small and medium-scale RIs.

Una Europa universities will work together on a **Position paper** aimed at promoting the interests of small and medium-sized RIs, and offering valuable insights into the kinds of organisational and funding support that they require. In order to bolster this argument, Una Europa will highlight the distinctive research assets of small and medium-sized RIs, as well as new collaboration models through creation of explicit connections and synergies that they will develop. We aim to demonstrate that despite their smaller scale, these RIs are highly research-intensive and often specialised and make valuable contributions to the broader research community supporting the backbone of strategic priorities on research and innovation (cf. D1.2)

The perspective of the Alliance will complement the position of other networks in which our partner universities participate, such as LERU and the Guild, bringing the specific point of view of a European University Alliance that has undertaken concrete steps towards institutional changes aimed at sharing RIs. To increase our impact, we will collaborate with other European University Alliances working on the transformation module aimed at sharing RIs: a joint position paper will be the key **to convey strategic messages to EU policy makers** in a more effective and impactful way.

1.3.3 Proposed action plan

Action 1: Adoption of coordinated visions and common principles for opening and sharing RIs

Level of ambition	Low	Medium	High
	Formulation of coordinated visions for opening and sharing RIs (e.g., Una Europa position paper)	Drafting the Una Europa Charter for Research Infrastructures (including the creation of a checklist for RIs, user safety policies, etc.). Based on the analysis of barriers and identification of common principles in Pillar 1 - Action 1 Implementation of awareness-raising activities	Adoption and promotion of the Una Europa Charter for Research Infrastructures Implementation of awareness-raising activities and showcase of flagship RIs
Actors	RI experts and managers, open data managers in consultation with policy makers; Self-Steering committees	RI experts and managers, open data managers in consultation with policy makers; Self-Steering committees	RI experts and managers, open data managers in consultation with policy makers; Self-Steering committees
Beneficiaries	RI managers; researchers; other universities and European Universities Alliances	RI managers; researchers; other universities and European Universities Alliances	RI managers; researchers; other universities and European Universities Alliances; external users of RIs

Overall requirement for Action 1 (and related risk): Institutional commitment and willingness to develop coordinated positions on opening and sharing RIs and make these positions official through position papers and a common Charter for RIs; the risk is that the diversity of institutional strategies and policies will not allow to achieve coordinated visions and agree on common principles at the Alliance level. Lack of funding targeting RIs and enabling the implementation of policies regarding accessibility and openness is another risk.

Action 2: Formulation of strategic messages towards the EC

Level of ambition	Low	Medium	High
	Participation in the stakeholders' consultations (both specifically focused on RI and consultations for European Universities and ERA in general)	Una Europa Position paper on instruments reinforcing small and medium-size RIs with a view to sharing them across the Alliance	Joint position paper with other European universities alliances , in synergy with other networks (e.g., LERU, The Guild, EUA), on instruments targeted to small and medium-size RIs (addressing challenges and reinforcing their value) to bring about institutional transformation towards sharing RIs
Actors	Una Europa vzw, RI Cluster/RI experts, policy makers, research funding officers and policy officers	Una Europa vzw, RI cluster/RI experts, policy makers, research funding officers and policy officers	Una Europa vzw, other European Universities Alliances, RI cluster/RI experts, policy makers, research funding officers and policy officers
Beneficiaries	Researchers (Self-Steering Committees), small and medium-size RIs of Una Europa, other universities, consortia and alliances	Researchers (Self-Steering Committees), small and medium-size RIs of Una Europa, other universities, consortia and alliances	Researchers (Self-Steering Committees), small and medium-size RIs of Una Europa, other universities, consortia and alliances

Overall requirement for Action 1 (and related risk): The commitment of Una Europa universities to engage in/actively promote discussion and stakeholders' consultations at European and national level is required to implement this action; the risk is minimal since Una Europa universities are already well positioned in their national research systems and, at European level, Una Europa vzw represents the Alliance and effectively coordinate/consult members vis-à-vis EU consultations. On the other hand, the institutional commitment of Una Europa universities and their willingness to formulate coordinated strategic messages towards the EC is needed.

1.3.4 Resources

The suggested actions require both expertise and active participation of Clusters of experts in Research Infrastructures and Open Research. This means that the main activities leading to the achievement of the actions of all levels of ambition can rely on institutional staff of member universities.

It will also require a significant engagement of research infrastructures, libraries and data centre's staff who will be the actors and main producers of the abovementioned activities and documents.

As for the adoption and implementation of the Una Europa Charter for RIs, which is an action of a high ambition, it will require additional funding targeting RIs themselves and enabling the implementation of policies regarding accessibility and openness.

The actions foreseen for strengthening Una Europa position on RIs on the European level will demand the active role of Una Europa vzw staff who are strategically located in Brussels and represent Una Europa in front of the European Commission.

SECTION 2 – Annexes: Reports of activities feeding into the Strategy and Action Plan for sharing and opening up research and data infrastructures

This section includes the detailed reports of the the activities carried out in Una.Resin WP2. These documents describe the background, methodology, and outcomes/recommendations of the activities, and crucially support the Strategy and action plan for sharing and opening up RIs presented in Section 1. The reports were shared with the stakeholders that were engaged in the actions and their feedback was integrated in the final version.

2.1 Report on the co-creation workshop “From mapping to co-creation: towards a Una Europa Strategy and Action Plan for sharing Research Infrastructures and Resources”

Introduction

The **Una.Resin WP2 “Research Infrastructures and Resources”** aims to develop a strategy and action plan for sharing research infrastructures across Una Europa universities and start exploring concrete paths and sharing formats. The work is focused on two global interdisciplinary challenges focused on Cultural Heritage and One Health, but also with a connection to the 4 other focus areas of the Alliance: European Studies, Sustainability, Data Science and Artificial Intelligence (AI). The implementation foresees 5 phases: (i) mapping of research infrastructures; (ii) development of a shared strategy and action plan; (iii) implementation of two pilot actions; (iv) evaluation of the pilot actions; v. dissemination on findings and recommendations.

In the first year of the project, WP2 focused on a threefold mapping exercise: (i) benchmarking Una Europa member universities’ RIs strategies, policies, initiatives, including funding mechanisms, organizational, and management models; (ii) mapping of the RIs related to the challenge “Exploring cultural heritage to strengthen inclusion and participative communities”; (iii) mapping of the RIs related to the challenge “Promoting the wellbeing of human and animals in a sustainable and healthy environment”. The analysis on the data collected led to the findings and considerations that constitute the basis of the co-creation workshop.

The **co-creation workshop** was aimed to connect the first and the second phase of WP2. The main results obtained during the first year have been further discussed with **RI experts** of all Una Europa universities. By working on **4 topics** resulting from the mapping exercises, the discussion led to collect further refinement/definition of **inputs, insights and ideas** that were used **to develop the strategy and the action plan for the future sharing of the RIs of Una Europa**.

Methodology

Agenda

The WP2 co-creation workshop “From mapping to co-creation: towards a Una Europa Strategy and Action plan for sharing Research Infrastructures and Resources” was held online on the 23rd of June 2022 from 10:00 to 13:30.

The workshop was divided in two parts: *Presentations session* and *Co-creation exercise*. The first session, open upon invitation, was dedicated to the presentations of two relevant RIs from the Cultural Heritage and the One Health field and the presentation of key results from the WP2 mapping exercise. The second session was dedicated to in-depth discussions by 6 participants from each university (3 in the field of Cultural Heritage and 3 in the field of One Health). The participants were divided in groups in 8 breakout rooms.

The second session was introduced by a presentation on how to participate within a breakout room both from a technical and thematic point of view. Each room was asked to discuss on **4 topics** that emerged from the benchmarking and the thematic mapping exercises previously implemented by WP2:

- relevant principles for opening and sharing RIs across universities;
- funding opportunities to stimulate interuniversity cooperation around RIs;
- strengthening skills and knowledge related to RIs management;
- overcoming barriers to share RIs.

The discussions were supported by the use of a Miro board divided in 8 rooms. The participants were asked to fill in the board with some keywords. The final Miro board has been also analysed to be included within this report.

At the end of the workshop, during a final plenary session, the interventions of the participants focused on specific topics which emerged during the discussions within the breakout rooms. The discussions held in the 8 breakout rooms, as well as the conclusions, were recorded to be used afterwards during the reporting phase.

Selection of participants

The attendees of the presentations session were invited by each university taking into considerations the possibility to invite their internal stakeholders in the field of Cultural Heritage and One Health, such as the representatives of the RIs mapped in the WP2 mapping exercises and other relevant RIs, as well as the members of the relevant Self-Steering Committees. A total of 25 persons participated along with the 62 that afterwards attended the co-creation exercise for a total of 87 participants (including WP members) logged in.

The participants in the Co-creation exercise were selected by the 8 universities, mainly among the academic community that contributed to the two thematic exercises focused on Cultural Heritage and One Health by filling out the questionnaires. Indeed, this choice contributed to keeping the relevant actors involved in the process by sharing the results of the mapping phase and discussing the next steps.

The Research Infrastructure Cluster’s members of each university were asked to identify and involve 6 representatives: 3 in the field of Cultural Heritage and 3 in the field of One Health. These were mainly researchers but also SSCs members with relevant expertise in Research Infrastructures and technicians and facility managers that were involved in the thematic mapping exercises as respondents of the questionnaires. The universities were asked to appoint representatives taking into consideration a differentiation of the participants in terms of expertise in different types of infrastructure (archives, digital infrastructure, laboratory, etc.), disciplinary background and/or different competences/profiles (researcher, technician, manager, etc.).

All universities appointed their representatives; to summarize, FUB involved 6 participants while KU Leuven, UCM, Unibo and JU 7 and UEDIN, UP1, UH 4, for a total of 46 participants took part in this co-creation exercise. The distribution of participants between the breakout rooms was based on the different expertise, universities, and typologies of infrastructure. In the following table, the 8 breakout rooms with the expertise of the participants involved are shown. The table summarises the organization of the breakout rooms, specifying the expertise of the participants.

Room	University	Department/Faculty/Centre	Type of expertise
1	FUB	University Library	Library systems
1	KU Leuven	University Library	Digitization and Document Delivery
1	UCM	Library Central Services	Library systems
1	UH	National Library of Finland	Library systems
1	UEDIN	University Library	Early printed books and photography

1	UP1	BIS Library	Manuscripts curation and valorization, cultural heritage, History, digitalization
2	UCM	Vice-Rector for Culture, Sport and University Extension-Professor, Department of Painting and Conservation - Restoration/Fine Arts/UCM	Specialist in museology and university heritage
2	Unibo	Dep of Architecture	Preservation and conservation of historical monuments and sites
2	Unibo	Dep of Cultural Heritage	Analysis of human skeletal remains using traditional and innovative virtual approaches
2	JU	The JU University Museum	Museology; Senior documentarian
2	JU	The JU University Museum	Museum curator, deputy director of the JU Museum
3	FUB	University Library	Special collections
3	KU Leuven	University Library	Digitization, integration & delivery
3	UH	Dept of Digital Humanities	Digital language data
3	Unibo	Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies	Cultural heritage sustainability and inclusiveness
3	UP1	LAMOP research unit	History, geography, cultural heritage, digital humanities
3	JU	Department of Anthropology of Literature and Cultural Studies	Video games
4	FUB	Central administration	The participant did not explicit its type of expertise
4	KU Leuven	Faculty of Arts	Valorization of cultural heritage, related to KIC CCSI
4	UCM	Vice-Rector for Culture, Sport and University Extension- Professor, Department Prehistory, Ancient History and Archaeology/Geography and History/UCM	Specialist in cultural heritage management

4	UH	Dept of Cultures	Folklore data
4	UP1	EIREST Research team (IREST Research Unit)	Cultural Heritage, Tourism, Creative Industries,
4	JU	Laboratory of Modern Polish History	20th century history
5	FUB	Institute of Chemistry and Biochemistry	Electron Microscopy
5	KU Leuven	Faculty of Bioscience Engineering	Animal and Human Health Engineering
5	UCM	Department of Microbiology and Parasitology	Fungal Genomics
5	Unibo	Dep of Electronic, electrical and information engineering	Electronic engineering
5	UEDIN	Centre for Inflammation Research	Flow Cytometry & Cell Sorting
5	JU	Medical department	Molecular Medical Microbiology
6	KU Leuven	Department of Human Genetics	KU Leuven Institute for Single Cell Omics (LISCO)
6	UCM	Department of Immunology. School of Medicine	Immunology, Cell Biology
6	UH	Helsinki Institute of Life Science (HiLIFE)/Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland (FIMM)	Genetics, developmental biology, physiology
6	Unibo	DIMEC	Biomedical and clinical research
6	UEDIN	Roslin Institute	Proteomics & Metabolomics
7	FUB	Department of Mathematics and Computer Science	Bioinformatics
7	KU Leuven	Department of Human Genetics	Genomics Core Leuven
7	UEDIN	Edinburgh Clinical Research Facility	Image Analysis
7	UP1	Centre of Economic Studies	Behavioural Studies
7	UJ	Faculty of Biochemistry, Biophysics and Biotechnology	Cell Biology

7	Unibo	Department of Agricultural and Food Sciences	Impact analysis of the common agricultural policy (CAP)
8	FUB	Institute of Chemistry and Biochemistry	Hydrogels
8	KU Leuven	Transfarm	Biomedical research, sustainable animal research, circulate economy
8	UCM	Department of Animal Health	The participant did not explicit its type of expertise
8	Unibo	Dep of Medical Veterinary Sciences DIMEVET	Biology of vascular cells
8	JU	Department of Biology	Physiology and Toxicology of Reproduction
8	UCM	Department of Microbiology II	Microbiology

In addition to the participants in the *Co-creation exercise*, 1 facilitator and 1 note-keeper were present in each breakout room. As for the facilitators, the task was to moderate the discussion within the breakout rooms, while the note keepers took notes during the discussion. The facilitators were briefed about their tasks by the WP2 team during two preparatory meetings a few weeks before the co-creation workshop.

It is worth mentioning that members of the Cluster Research Infrastructure were involved as facilitators of the breakout rooms.

The total number of participants in the *Co-creation exercise* was 62 (46 participants, 8 facilitators and 8 note keepers).

Framework for the workshop: major results of the mapping exercises

The co-creation workshop's framework was designed to share and gather insights from the participants on four main topics based on the conclusions of the Deliverable 2.1 "Mapping RIRs and priorities for joint strategy". The study framework constituted the basis of the four guiding topics discussed within the breakout rooms.

- The analysis made within the mapping exercise "Benchmarking Una Europa member universities' RIs strategies, policies, initiatives" led to consider the need to agree on **common guiding principles**, on which it is possible to rely to build our ecosystem of RIs for Research, Innovation and Education within Una Europa. A possible way is the co-designing of a Charter for RIs that would encourage the adoption of principles in order to lay the groundwork for a joint strategy and action plan for RIs.

- The thematic mappings focused on **Cultural Heritage** and **One Health** revealed that the limited sharing capacities due to financial constraints is considered by the academic community as a major obstacle that could hamper collaboration with other universities. The deliverable report "Benchmarking Una Europa member universities' RIs strategies, policies, initiatives" has even more highlighted that small and medium-sized RIs are confronted with a severe **lack of funding**. Finally, from the three thematic mapping exercises emerged clearly the need for **(inter)national financing programmes/Una Europa seed funding** to stimulate interuniversity collaborations around RIs. Indeed, most of the EU funds available to Una Europa institutions are mainly targeted towards larger-scale infrastructures. Una Europa support could have a pivotal role in this regard: by creating a common space for knowledge, tools and practices exchanges and by offering ramp-up funding (if feasible), opening and sharing of RIs can be significantly accelerated. Indeed, to allocate seed funding for initial research collaborations or short mobilities of researchers and RIs managers for the opening and sharing of RIs, could be a first stimulus to test the feasibility of cross-institutional access to RIs.
- The thematic mapping focused on Cultural Heritage and One Health confirmed that from the academic community's point of view, there is a **need for experts, researchers and RIs managers** to ensure upgrading, opening and sharing RIs across our universities. This is particularly true within the One Health group of RIs that answered the questionnaire of the mapping exercise. A relevant item that emerged from all three thematic mapping exercises is the need to **strengthen the skills and knowledge related to RIs management**. The benchmarking mapping led to consider that to manage RIs according to similar principles is a prerequisite to ease their opening and sharing at the Una Europa level and beyond. In this regard, focusing on improving the specific skills of personnel involved in the management of RIs is fundamental. The most added value for Una Europa would be to strengthen skills and knowledge related to RIs management through a **mutual learning process** building on the existing initiatives and structures (e.g., Una Europa Clusters expertise, staff mobility schemes, etc.) and drawing on the richness and complementary strengths of Una Europa Universities. Mobility of staff between Una universities in a multidisciplinary and transnational perspective would be central in this mutual learning process. Actions directed towards this mutual learning process could start from the ongoing mobility initiatives (e.g., "Live my life" joint format for job shadowing), ongoing projects like RitrainPlus^[1]) and would develop new formats, such as webinars on RIs-related topics (such as developing and interconnecting RIs tools including database, software, research archives etc.), and targeted seminars/workshop open to all stakeholders including external researchers, the business community, and citizens. Open Science principles will play an important role in this process.
- The mapping of the RIs related to the challenge "Exploring **cultural heritage** to strengthen inclusion and participative communities" highlighted the major obstacles that

could hamper collaboration with other universities: i. limited access and sharing capacities due to **financial constraints**; ii. access restrictions due to registration constraints and **bureaucracy**; iii. restrictions due to **legal rules, compliance with ethical and privacy regulations** or other regulatory constraints e.g., IPR, copyright, third parties IP rights, inconsistent application of fairness principles, and safety rules. Other barriers are represented by **language**, access limitations due to a **lack of specialized staff** and limited capacities due to **physical** (e.g., lack of space), **technical and technological constraints**.

- The mapping of the RIs related to the challenge “Promoting the wellbeing of human and animals in a sustainable and healthy environment (**One Health**)” highlighted the major obstacles that could hamper collaboration with other universities: i. limitations connected to a **lack of qualified staff**; ii. registration and **bureaucratic constraints**; iii. the limited sharing capacities due to **financial constraints** and iv. lack of funds. It is particularly important to note that in the field of OH, a major issue is the **compliance with ethical and privacy regulations**. Other barriers are represented by restrictions due to **legal rules** or regulatory constraints such as IPR, copyright, third parties IP rights, inconsistent application of fairness principles, privacy and safety rules; limited capacities due to **physical** (e.g., lack of space), **technical and technological constraints (inaccessibility of external users); Open Data policies**.

On the basis of the mapping exercise, questions were formulated and shared with the participants before the break-out sessions. In particular, the participants in the co-creation exercise received the concept note of the event (containing the agenda, the framework information and the questions to be discussed), the synthesis of the deliverable 2.1, the list of the infrastructures mapped within the Cultural Heritage and One Health fields during the first phase of the project implementation and the description of the participants in the 8 breakout rooms. The facilitators and the note keepers received the same materials and also a guidelines document created to explain how to manage a breakout room and to use the Miro board. Some institutions (e.g., KU Leuven) prepared a pre-briefing meeting before the workshops with their participants to explain the methodology.

Questions discussed during the workshop

The following four questions were discussed during the workshop:

1. What are, in your opinion, the **relevant principles for opening and sharing RIs** between universities? Please list and describe these principles, assessing the feasibility and specifying the relevant actors involved.

Examples:

a) widen and ease access to external academic and non-academic partners (industrials, civil society, citizens);

- b) favour openness of tools and data (ensure FAIRness principles);
- c) encourage long-term and sustainable managerial models and practices (e.g., adapted pricing system and business model, managing committee...);
- d) organise teaching, training and seminars.

2. We would like to understand which **types of funding** (e.g., for mobility, for collaborative research projects, etc.) could help stimulate interuniversity collaborations around RIs. Can you describe the **funding needs related to opening/sharing RIs** and how these needs should be addressed?

For example: do you see the need for a **seed funding call** funded by Una Europa and/or other external funding sources (European, national, regional) to stimulate joint collaborations between RIs?

3. Which **skills and knowledge related to RIs** management should be strengthened in order to enable the sharing of RIs across Una Europa universities?

Which initiatives could be taken towards this **mutual learning process** (e.g., webinars, job shadowing, etc.)? Which kind of knowledge should be exchanged, in particular through mobility?

4. Lack of funding and lack of skills/knowledge related to RIs (discussed in questions n. 2 and 3) are the most relevant barriers in the Cultural Heritage and One Health fields respectively. Considering the **other barriers to share RIs** (see list below) that emerged from the mapping exercise: which actions in your thematic fields (Cultural Heritage or One Health) could be taken to overcome these barriers? Define **possible actions** per barrier.

Results from the thematic mapping One Health

1. access to the RIs restricted by registration constraints
2. the clearance of ethical and privacy rights required to conduct experiments and valorise research results
3. limited capacities due to physical (e.g., lack of space), technical and technological constraints
4. compliance with Open Data rules
5. language

Results from the thematic mapping Cultural Heritage

1. access to the RIs restricted by registration constraints
2. legal constraints (mainly Intellectual Property rules but also difficulties in implementing fairness data principles related to accessibility, privacy and safety rules).
3. Language
4. limited capacities due to physical (e.g., lack of space), technical and technological constraints (e.g., lack of specific tools)

Outcome of the discussions in the break-out rooms

1. Relevant principles for opening and sharing RIs across universities

*Q. What are, in your opinion, the **relevant principles** for opening and sharing RIs between universities? Please list and describe these principles, assessing the feasibility and specifying the relevant actors involved.*

Set full accessibility across institutions

An issue quoted by some participants is how to give access to external users to the electronical resources of an institution. In fact, internal users have full access to the resources, while it is not always possible to give full access to external users. An identification system that gives access to data at different levels (e.g.,: administrator, user, etc.) would be required.

Easy and standardised access to the RIs is required also to optimize the booking of the RIs. At FUB, a specific software is available, OpenIRIS, that allows users to search for specific equipment and infrastructures and book them as well.

A prioritising system could be useful since there could be a higher demand than what time capacity allows. If the RIs is full, the users could get in contact with the person in charge to arrange a time to use it.

Agreements across different universities also could affect the accessibility of RIs. A common template at Alliance level would ease the work of legal teams at institution level, which usually have to agree on the terms and conditions to produce an agreement to work together.

Ensure openness through applying FAIR data principles

The openness principle has been quoted by the majority of the breakout rooms. It is intended as both openness of the access to physical collections and openness of data. Some participants explicitly mentioned the FAIR data principles.

It is worth to underline that the need of openness often starts at the level of each university and even at the level of the departments: what emerged in the discussion is that sometimes it is difficult to share research infrastructures and even know each other inside a department.

A couple of threats related to the openness that should be considered are the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) constraints and the ethical issues. The possibility to develop a uniform approach to GDPR and ethical issues within Una Europa should be strongly taken into consideration.

Develop tools to foster collaboration

Collaborating and working together was mentioned as a key principle to allow knowledge transfer between universities and to foster research collaboration. The need for institutional information providing an overview of core facilities and IT services emerged as a preliminary

condition to share knowledge and technology across Una Europa institutions. The threat is represented by the substantial different modalities of cataloguing across institutions.

A specific need emerged from one of the CH breakout rooms: to collaborate between libraries and research institutions. This item has been raised to avoid that libraries take only the role of data provider; indeed, it was suggested to foresee for them a role closer to the research institution.

Enhanced communication and dissemination

Communication was mentioned as a key principle. Communication is targeted to both internal and external audience and is defined in a broad sense, including communication among small teams, among infrastructures and universities, and at the national and transnational level.

It was highlighted that communication among researchers and infrastructures within and across institutions should be improved and that more national and transnational connection and networking is required.

The Huma-num consortium could be a possible benchmark.

Professional skills

The participants underlined the difference between scientists and managers within the context of a facility or RIs: both profiles are needed due to their different points of views.

TRANSfarm RI from KU Leuven emerged as a possible benchmark: TRANSfarm facilitates scientific research on a pilot scale in the broad research domains of the sustainable bioeconomy and translational biomedical research. During the workshop it was mentioned as a successful example in the involvement of different professional skills.

The different approaches in different countries, in terms of required professional skills and profiles considered, were mentioned as a barrier.

Standardising digitalisation of tools and skills

Some participants of the CH breakout rooms mentioned the digitalisation, since many institutions are believed to have basic digital infrastructures. In their opinion, nowadays it is fundamental to share advanced and complex datasets, such as digital images but also metadata about heritage collections, as well as principles for digital preservation.

Indeed, a standardisation of digital infrastructures (software coordination making it accessible across institutions) was proposed as a possible initiative towards shared assets. It is important to understand differences on digital infrastructures across universities and working towards the standardisation of the processes.

Data sharing to foster interdisciplinary approach

The exchange of different perspectives on a topic is very valuable: the interdisciplinary approach enriches the research. It will be important to foster data sharing and allow access to all types of data for multiple use.

Ensure quality digital catalogue to stimulate the use of RIs

Many RIs and resources are not used due to incomplete cataloguing, including provision of protocol: for this reason, RIs with high potential are not accessible.

In case of collections, it is important to share information, not only exploiting them. Indeed, to exchange different perspectives is believed to be very valuable: the interdisciplinary approach enriches the research.

What emerged in the discussion rooms is the need to have also a catalogue of services for the RIs where potential users can find all the details. The basis of a sharing process should be the description of what can be found in each university and in each infrastructure. Details and information on how to access the RIs are considered as basic information. This scenario could lead to create direct connections between the different research teams and universities.

Share best practices

The participants quickly mentioned the relevance of sharing best practices, e.g., data quality frameworks, data management plan, etc.

RIs and education

It is important to mention that the RIs could be connected to international PhD courses. It refers to the need to connect the use of the RIs to common educational perspectives (i.e., developing models for open educational resources), which could be a very relevant principle to be further developed. For example, there could be possibilities to develop innovative models in education and research based on Open Data and Open Research practices in Una Europa universities.

Safety issues

Safety can represent a barrier when external persons access the RIs. Safety barriers are not allowing the researchers to do some research, or the activity of the researcher is limited due to safety issues. While sharing facilities, the Alliance should ensure that all the institutions guarantee the same safety issues.

Users' agreements for internal and external use could be set specifying conditions on safety and experiences to use equipment in order to comply with the institutional rules (preferences for long-term than ad-hoc/short-term).

Mobility

Technical and scientific knowledge and expertise should be exchanged through mobility initiatives.

Sharing RIs means also sharing the possibility to train people working on RIs. For example, if a researcher needs to do some specific analysis, he/she could visit a specific facility and work together with the staff to learn the methodology. This point has been discussed further and it is possible to find more information in the following chapters.

Constant update of training

The specific idea that emerged in the discussion is that it is possible for labs to do bioinformatics by themselves, but it requires constant updating of training.

Constant update of technologies

Constant updating of technologies in the field is key to enable research and services to the wider community. This point has been discussed further; more information can be found in the following chapters.

Common EU funding

RIs should be used in the framework of common projects. Research projects need to be connected to infrastructures projects. It would be useful to have an infrastructure database to seek for further collaborations and initiate possible new grant applications. This point has been discussed further; more information can be found in the following chapters.

Common pricing model

Fostering a common pricing model and adapting the pricing model in relation to type of user emerged as important principles for sharing RIs: in particular it is important to distinguish: full cost for non-academic partners and academic partners with no collaboration; potential and minimal costs (e.g., only consumables) for other categories.

Balance of excellent research and services to the research communities

The balance between being a research centre and service centre was discussed but it was not fully developed during the discussion. It refers to the equilibrium between the two main functions of a RIs.

Continuous innovation

The need for continuous innovation of core facilities was mentioned to create strong foundations for both research and services. For this purpose, RIs need to:

- show academic outputs (e.g., produce methodological articles);
- balance between being a research centre and service centre; here it would be interesting to understand how the university sees this, and to share practices on how each institution approaches this balance;
- divide tasks/roles;
- training and job-shadowing.

Overview on relevant principles

The following common main principles have been mentioned both in the CH and OH breakout rooms:

- guarantee the full accessibility of digital and physical RIs to external users;
- ensure the openness of the access to physical collections and openness of data;
- develop tools to foster collaboration and allow knowledge transfer;
- involvement of different professional skills in the RIs;
- standardising digitalisation of tools and skills to share advanced and complex datasets.

The list of specific principles mentioned only in CH breakout rooms is the following:

- enhanced communication and dissemination;
- data sharing to foster interdisciplinary approach;
- ensure quality digital catalogue to stimulate the use of RIs.

The list of specific principles mentioned only in OH breakout rooms is the following:

- create the conditions to share best practices within the alliance;
- create the conditions to attract students and researchers;
- ensure the connection between RIs and education;
- ensure that all the institutions guarantee the same safety issues;
- exchange knowledge and expertise through mobility initiatives;
- constant update of training;
- research projects need to be connected to infrastructures projects;
- fostering a common pricing model;
- ensure the balance between being a research centre and service centre.

2. Funding opportunities to stimulate interuniversity cooperation around RIs

*Q. We would like to understand which **types of funding** (e.g., for mobility, for collaborative research projects, etc.) could help stimulate interuniversity collaborations around RIs. Can you*

*describe the **funding needs related to opening/sharing RIs** and how these needs should be addressed?*

Funding for mobility to increase the knowledge about the available RIs

Mobility is considered a key issue because it allows to work together and learn from each other (share expertise, tools, infrastructures).

Physical mobility and virtual mobility are both useful. However, meeting in person, talking to people, watching collections in presence is much more effective. The participants proposed an internship of 1 week or a longer even with residence module (6 months) to share ideas and develop also an output in 6 months: this is a real case running in Finland where this kind of residence modules have been successfully implemented.

Some participants reported that within their institution they have funds to visit other universities and libraries, but these funds should be more focused on research project visit and creating working teams. The exchange of people does not only have to focus on researchers but also on technicians. There are no opportunities of mobility for technicians: this needs to be improved.

The topic of mobility is also connected to the need of having a more systematic networking. Visiting infrastructures is good for trainings of students: they bring back new experiences. Some universities already offer internships, but it would be good to open to students from other universities. The Erasmus+ programme has been mentioned as a possible opportunity for traineeship. Another point that emerged from the breakout rooms was the need to take part in study visits, not only teaching activities.

Funding for interoperability

Interoperability has been mentioned as a possible way to create joint corpora to enrich data.

Funding to stimulate teamwork and collaborations

Teamwork and collaborations are important to overcome the “silos” of individual departments and connect different practices. It is important to know each other, know what the other institutions and persons do, to be able to collaborate.

Funding could be the way to go forward and propose new project initiatives on topics on which there are possibilities to collaborate. On this point, it emerged as relevant to work with other institutions at national level, involving ministries, academies, cities, and other local associations.

Funding for doing surveys on the status of heritage’s collection

Funding could be used to run separate surveys on the status of heritage’s collections to understand what other partners are using to create their collections. This point was not further

developed during the discussion. However, it could be intended as a concrete step towards sharing RIs within CH field.

Funding to build new RIs

Funds are needed to build new infrastructures and hire professional people to run these infrastructures. It is worth noting that the need for building new infrastructures has emerged also during the thematic mapping exercise.

Funding for personnel with different skills/expertise and training

Funding opportunities were mentioned as a suggestion to overcome the lack of personnel.

In terms of expertise, it was mentioned that finding skilled personnel with IT background is usually very difficult; there is also a lack of human resources with curatorial background. On this topic, it was suggested to have private-public collaborations and ensure the availability of enterprise opportunities .

Another issue regards the intellectual property; specialised personnel with specific skills on IPR management to support the RIs is needed. Specific staff should also take care of the RIs catalogue and update information.

During the workshop it was also proposed to organise trainings devoted to strengthening capacities of managers at host institutions. However, the mobility of technicians needs more attention, due to the fact that it may jeopardize daily activities at core facilities (i. e. labs) and also impact on funding of facility staff for external guests.

Funding to create digital models to compare data

From a CH breakout room emerged the importance of sharing digital models. This would help to overcome the barrier of the lack of shared data. For example, funds may be requested for biomechanical analysis of bones with digital models to compare them with data between countries.

It has been recommended to work to set-up general principles regarding data models, formats, and instructions to create harmonised data.

Digitalisation is intended to share common principles but also common standards to make the knowledge accessible. For example, the [project 4CH](#) has the role to allow sharing knowledge and data about CH. EC is aware about the relevance of the topic: the pressure to speed up digitalisation is a cross-domain issue.

Some participants pointed out that it is easier to get funding for digitalisation than literary studies.

It was also mentioned that, with the amount of data that has to be handled, it is necessary to refer to commercial companies.

Seed funding

Seed funding is an important initiative and a good step to set priorities and to start joint involvement in other programmes. Several ideas were suggested, partially overlapping with the abovementioned suggestions in terms of funding.

In order to get to know each other better in the first phase, funding could be used by building sub-groups within the network. Some participants proposed to use seed funding for smaller research projects along with third-party funding, stimulating cross-institutional research. It could also be used for mobility or to maintain the research infrastructure.

It was proposed that seed funding could also be used to set up trainings and workshops through physical visits, online format (on-line courses on data, analysis etc.), and trips devoted to managers to upgrade their expertise, stimulating the motivation of the people involved in RIs. As it is perceived as difficult to get project funding for this topic, costs could be borne by universities through structural funds.

Seed funding was also suggested for developing new methods. In particular, a best practice was presented by KU Leuven on ID-N funds used for consumables, to stimulate research groups to work together on multidisciplinary topics and repeat that in Una Europa.

The existing Una Europa seed funding should be more focused on RIs: right now, it is much more focused on the research and network collaboration building. For the next calls, more emphasis could be put on RIs initiatives.

Funding to develop a digital catalogue of infrastructures

There should be an online catalogue that is easily accessible for everyone to see which RIs are available at the universities of the Alliance. This first step of knowing what infrastructures are available is of huge importance.

The point is not just to know it, it is also important to keep this catalogue updated. Indeed, in Edinburgh also, while doing the mapping from One Health, many infrastructures were discovered that had not been mapped previously.

A catalogue could ease the process to have coordinated services; indeed, infrastructure is about serving research groups.

Moreover, mapping where RIs have similar user groups is interesting, since RIs could serve these users together.

Funding from private companies

Technology transfer could be used to ensure the return on investments. In some cases, it is possible to provide services and patents and it is possible to pay personnel with the fees paid by industry.

Most of those that need training are students. However, in many cases, there are external people that need training or re-training. If companies know that they can get training at Una Europa, then they could pay to train their personnel, and this would result in funding for the infrastructures.

Spin-off companies could support the joint initiatives with a small percentage of their revenue.

Permanent funding

Usually, researchers work on a RIs for a limited time. Consequently, infrastructures should not be modelled on temporary research project funding but needs to have a permanent funding plan. It is important to guarantee a permanent availability of results which came out of a project. This issue should be addressed from a structural point of view.

Stimulate collaborative methods

It was suggested to use funding to stimulate the development of collaborative methods. For example, the possibility emerged to create intergenerational cohorts of technical managers to take part in trainings devoted to strengthening capacities of managers at host institutions. UK has a best practice named “technologist training” to recognize their expertise and skills.

Funding for communication and dissemination

Seed funding could be used to upgrade communication and dissemination: the need for a dedicated person to “market” core facilities was highlighted. This goes beyond managing websites and social media. The participants mentioned the good practice of VIB - Flemish institute for Biotechnology (KU Leuven).

Spillover effects can be used to strengthen valorisation aspects (i.e., improved outreach, outward communication and marketing). This topic itself can open a wide range of funding possibilities.

Allocate funds for the conferences on RIs

Funding for international conferences on RIs was also proposed. Facility staff, researchers, PhD students could participate in conferences dedicated to RIs in order to raise the profile of all RIs, and give recognitions to the RIs experts; it would be interesting to present successful case studies.

Funding for engaging more early-career researchers

Usually there is a small amount of money for early-career researchers. An increase of funding could have a positive impact and help the interactions across RIs. Research realised by younger researchers can be considered an opportunity to learn and build up experience to apply for larger funds.

Funding for maintenance of RIs

Being able to maintain RIs is a problem that emerged during the workshop. Seed funding for research is useful, as long as there is also funding for maintenance. Currently, funds for the research projects are available but not for the maintenance of RIs. For example, a new microscope: a research group needs to be able to establish the instrument and to maintain it. For this purpose, bigger grants would be necessary to support the needs of the RIs.

Possible funding for COST action

COST actions have been mentioned since they represent a very flexible tool that could be useful to connect people and thus lay the basis for sharing RIs. Funds are granted to connect people in a wide range of actions. But for bigger groups those types of actions are not enough; for example, COST would not be the appropriate programme to maintain technologies. However, networking and community building among RIs experts are paramount: it was mentioned in the discussion that there are for example some sub-fields in OH that strongly need to bring people together in order to be able to implement collaborative research and share RIs.

Users shift

Concerning co-financing, it is quite complicated to equally share the infrastructures among the users. If the infrastructure is successful there are a lot of demands. It is important to distinguish and find a healthy balance between external and internal users. It must be highlighted that external users generate the majority of the income.

Overview on types of funding

The types of funding needs that emerged from both in the CH and OH breakout rooms are the following:

- mobility to increase the knowledge about the available RIs, which is also the most frequently quoted item;
- funding for personnel with different skills/expertise and training;
- create digital models to compare data and more in general improve the digitalisation and sharing of data;
- seed funding, which is considered as a useful instrument to improve the sharing from different points of view;
- an online catalogue of infrastructures: this is considered as the basis to enable different paths of sharing.

The specific funding needs mentioned in the CH breakout rooms are the following:

- interoperability, which has been mentioned as a possible way to create joint corpora to enrich data;
- funding to stimulate teamwork and collaborations to overcome the “silos” of individual departments and connect different practices;
- funding for doing surveys on the status of heritages’ collections;
- funds are needed to build new infrastructures and hire professionals;
- permanent funding plan to ensure the availability of results.

The specific funding needs mentioned in the OH breakout rooms are the following:

- funding from private companies should be considered as a new possibility;
- stimulate the development of collaborative methods;
- improve the communication and dissemination;
- ensure the participation of staff, researchers, PhD students in conferences on RIs;
- funding for engaging more early-career researchers;
- funding for maintenance of RIs;
- possible funding for COST action to connect people;
- consider the share of co-financing of the infrastructures to better balance external and internal users.

3. Strengthening skills and knowledge related to RIs management

*Q. Which **skills and knowledge related to RIs management** should be strengthened in order to enable the sharing of RIs across Una Europa universities? Which initiatives could be taken towards this **mutual learning process** (e.g., webinars, job shadowing, etc.)? Which kind of knowledge should be exchanged, in particular through mobility?*

Management skills

Management skills are needed to shift from an institution-based use of a research infrastructure to a shared use. Sharing these skills and practical aspects would be fundamental across facilities, especially core facilities.

It was mentioned that an upgrade on knowledge should address all aspects of RIs management: administrative/finance, management people, law, safety, constraints, and waste management. A RIs manager requires all sorts of skills and knowledge in addition to the research expertise.

Trainings focused on RIs management already exist, but are mostly related to writing grants, while something new is needed: training to manage people, groups, grants, and also infrastructures.

Research requires training on how to analyse a workflow; how to determine who is responsible for which domain. This type of training is helpful to develop the required skills in order to manage the complete workflow. Currently this type of training does only exist in companies, not within the universities.

Language skills

It is important to facilitate learning other languages. The issue of contexts where the majority of people do not have competencies in other languages emerged from the discussion. It is not only a matter of developing learning courses, but also of being in the place practicing the local language. Apart from the linguistic barriers, there are cultural barriers, so it might be difficult to understand each other even when speaking the same language.

Networking and skills for writing project proposals

Related to the possibility of applying for European funding, joining international networks is still considered as a critical issue: it is important to address this point, by facilitating networking. It is also important to consider the skills that needs to be acquired for writing project proposals at the European level.

IT competencies

It is difficult to hire enough IT skilled personnel to do the work at RIs facilities. If no IT experts are hired, then there is the need for the employees to learn and to be trained or re-trained in IT competencies, and this takes time.

Transversal and interdisciplinary knowledge

Dealing with different infrastructures, a specific OH problem is related to the interdisciplinarity: it is very relevant to create an interdisciplinary network of people.

Soft and horizontal skills

Management of infrastructures is something that requires not only hard but also soft skills. In order to create connections, soft skills in communications and languages are needed.

Museology

There should be specific trainings for specific skills: e.g., on museology, conservation, and documentation. UCM delivers trainings on these issues to the directors that are experts in other fields; they learn a lot from each other, and this affects also their capacity to take decisions. Initiatives could be taken towards this mutual learning process.

Catalogue of RIs to include trainings / digital platforms

A major point that emerged from the breakout rooms is the need for a catalogue/platform, or “ID for RIs”, where researchers can find all the information and promote workshops and meetings to exchange experiences and problems especially about management.

It was also emphasised the need to create a database for people applying for grants; it could include a mix of scientific, management, and dissemination tools. In general, the need to know each other was strongly expressed by the attendees. Participants believe that in the field of cultural heritage RIs are not known enough by others. This remains a challenge because people are too busy and getting to know each other is time consuming. It is very important to avoid creating new time-consuming processes.

It was also mentioned that the creation of a portal with available RIs, with suggestions for finding new ones would be very useful. Taxonomies can help understanding what an RI is about and how a RI can complement somebody’s research: this could improve networking across RIs. The realisation of a digital platform has been suggested in order to be used to ask collaborations with other research groups for matchmaking purposes. It could also be useful to construct a repository with all researchers’ contacts and also a kind of notice board in which it is possible to have a matchmaking of project ideas.

Modality of training: Mobility and staff exchanges

Staff exchanges should be focused on projects rather than general visits (also outside Europe). Annual staff exchange weeks and job shadowing have been also suggested. Technical and practical skills require in person interactions: workshops and meetings for related area managers could be realised. It is also important to foster mobility of people, i.e., bring together people who manage facilities. It is necessary to know each other, also through site visits at the research infrastructures across Una Europa universities. This requires some investments but then opportunities arise.

Staff exchanges are needed also for administrative staff; for example, for Italy it would be important to see how the other countries are working also at the administrative level.

Commercial courses

Some courses could be adopted from private companies’ existing modules and adapted for the EU framework. The advantage is that private companies usually are more updated, and a possible cooperation would be eased by a mutual interest. KU Leuven adapted some courses from private companies on workflow management (from the diagnostic sector) and these insights changed a lot how the work has been organised.

Overview on skills and knowledge

The skills that should be strengthened that were mentioned both in the CH and OH breakout rooms are the following:

- management skills, which is also the most frequently quoted skill;
- language skills;
- transversal and interdisciplinary knowledge;
- soft and horizontal skills which refer mainly to communication and dissemination.

The specific skills proposed in the CH breakout rooms are the following:

- networking to join international consortia;
- writing project proposal skills;
- develop IT competencies to work at RIs facilities;
- develop a training focused on museology, conservation, and documentation.

One specific skill to enhance that was proposed in the OH breakout rooms is the transversal and interdisciplinary knowledge.

Regarding the initiatives proposed that could help to develop these skills, a catalogue of RIs was mentioned again in both fields underlining the possibility to include trainings (digital platform). Other initiatives mentioned by the participants are the following: mobility and staff exchanges; the possibility to take courses from commercial companies and adapt for the EU framework.

4. Overcoming barriers to share RIs

*Q. Lack of funding and lack of skills/knowledge related to RIs (discussed in questions n.2 and 3) are the most relevant barriers in the Cultural Heritage and One Health fields respectively. Considering the **other barriers to share RIs** that emerged from the mapping exercise: which actions in your thematic fields (Cultural Heritage or One Health) could be taken to overcome these barriers? Define **possible actions** per barrier.*

Cultural Heritage Breakout rooms

Registration constraints

Open data policy should be applied for objects in the public domain by exporting data to different platforms and creating machine readable data for further processing.

It is necessary to consider that some infrastructures are open while others need passwords. This leads to the difference between sharing within a university and sharing with other universities.

At a more general level, the approach should be oriented to systematising and providing an overview of what the alliance already has (instead of adding something).

Legal constraints

Legal constraints are mainly related to Intellectual Property rules but also difficulties in implementing FAIR data principles related to accessibility and privacy and safety issues.

Adopting CC licenses was mentioned as a possible solution. If possible, it would also be useful to adopt common principles for open science (really open to the world, not just Europe-wide) and simplify copyright processes and restrictions. The new copyright legislation about the Digital Single Market is more complex than the previous one. It is really difficult to disseminate data, to send the data outside the country (Finland was mentioned by means of example), to be elaborated by more efficient computers. In order to avoid possible restrictions at national legislative levels, some partners started using and working in the public domain so that it is free for use by anyone and for any purpose without restriction under copyright law. The public domain is the purest form of open/free data, since no one owns or controls the material in any way.

It was suggested to develop tailored protocols targeting the specificity of the infrastructures and the specificity of local dimensions: it is important to understand local conditions and how to overcome possible barriers at this level. The engagement of legal and ethical officers within universities would help solve these specific problems: the creation of a task force was proposed.

Language

It would be important to encourage personnel to engage in staff exchange.

Creating shared multilingual thesauri for automatic translation would be helpful. It is important to consider that a lot of documentation is written in national languages: in big projects, documentation is done in English, while in smaller projects it is sometimes in national languages; machine translation can be useful; also, metadata and a brief introduction in frequently used language could be useful.

However, it was considered that language is not the most important barrier. On the one hand it may be considered as a barrier but, on the other hand, there is also an added value in getting in touch with other cultures. The importance of understanding the culture of the other countries was stressed.

Limited capacities due to physical (e.g., lack of space), technical and technological constraints (e.g., lack of specific tools)

The following ideas emerged in the discussion:

- Share the costs of physical infrastructures (e.g., server rooms) and dedicated personnel;
- Permanent positions for people being responsible for collections;
- Develop a clear user-guide describing physical, technical and technological features of the specific RI (e.g., area, maximum number of people admitted, required skills, etc.).

Further reflections and ideas on barriers not emergent during the mapping exercises

- More concise information about the work of Una Europa is needed: the academic community is not aware about the mission of Una Europa in relation to RIs;
- Mapping initiative should be done more often to have a more effective map of the infrastructures. The current report stemming from Una.Resin mapping exercise does not reflect the reality of the universities, since it includes only a small part of the comprehensive landscape of Una Europa infrastructures;
- In the field of video games, there is no public data, everything is kept secret and is the property of multinationals, prototypes of games are destroyed, updates of a game can be a political issue, but older versions get destroyed;
- It would be important to make a history of image distribution: there are currently no sources available;
- Project of social media archiving may have legal problems; Facebook and other platforms do not want to share the data; it is not possible to just buy a copy, like it was done for newspapers; Twitter has the complete archive online accessible for free.

One Health Breakout rooms

Registration constraints

One of the biggest barriers to using each other's facilities and equipment is the different ways in which the universities work. At the Edinburgh university, there are few facilities, and it is difficult even for internals to bring someone from a different campus to work in labs associated with an area. In order to work together it is important to make sure that easy access is created.

A clear workflow and an online registration tool are needed to help each other. Webinars for researchers and administrative personnel could be helpful. There must be an obvious person to contact: to know the manager/person in charge of the RIs makes everything easier – otherwise visitors and researchers don't know who to speak to and this creates difficulties.

There are no easy solutions to improving access due to the fact that it is needed to track down users, to check if people are authorised, and for the use of the infrastructure.

Some other short points of feedback on accessibility were collected:

- Give priority to local researchers' services: it is important to ensure capacity to deliver for internal use first;
- Distinguish between internal and external service implementation; distinguish different funding sources oriented towards internal and external users (funding for external users may be available in comparison to internal users); consider also that external researchers can attract additional funding.

The clearance of ethical and privacy rights required to conduct experiments and valorise research results

When doing experiments on animals or people it is necessary to apply to an ethical committee; from a practical point of view, it is possible to provide standard text to apply for ethical committees.

The following points should be taken into consideration:

- Having common contracts with IP and other aspects already established
- Having standard texts about the working of the RIs that can be used by the visiting researcher to apply for the EC
- Having dedicated personnel who help with regulations
- Having a board where multiple countries are represented that can help solve cross-country legal problems. Legal framework is fragmented in EU and it is not possible to be sure that what is done in a country can be done in another. A board could help solve some of those issues and give an answer to specific questions, by liaising with ethics committees.

Regarding ethical and privacy rights, it was suggested to check the country's regulations. There is a strong need to know what legal country requirements are applied. For instance, every human sample being brought into Belgium for registration must be registered at a bio-bank.

The role of ethical committees should be explained to people before they undertake a project, in order to clarify why there is the need for sharing infrastructures, how it will be done, and what the ethical impacts will be. If this point is clear, then it could alleviate any concerns that the ethic committee might have.

It was also considered that this approach of clarifying ethical impacts is getting more and more difficult, especially when it comes to genetic data. Extracting genetic data and identifying people has increased dramatically in recent years, with the related need to consider legal constraints. For this type of health sensitive data, having a federate analytics model where data is kept local is very helpful. There is significant discussion to be had on how to set this up. As soon as standard are reached, this initiative will be very powerful.

Limited capacities due to physical (e.g., lack of space), technical and technological constraints

Prioritising the use of RIs is considered helpful in case of excessive requests. For instance, internal users could have priority over external users and academic users could have priority on non-academic users. It is important to have a clear overview of other labs of the Alliance in the same field, using the same technology, that may have capacity.

It was also highlighted that data hosting is expensive, especially in International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO) certified repositories.

Open and collaborative RIs will allow facilities to embrace niche technology that can still become well-used through sharing.

Compliance with quality standards

It would be important to have some quality labels in order to prove that the infrastructure does stick to some guidelines and minimum quality. Therefore, there should be some guidelines and the possibility to give a label based on minimum standards. This should be connected also to the Charter of common principles in which there can be defined what the minimum quality standard needs to be for a research infrastructure.

Global standards could be taken as a benchmark. For example, in the field of cytometry the ISAC (International Society for Advancement of Cytometry) certification exists. It is considered highly regarded in the US but not so much in Europe. It could be beneficial to have something like this for Una Europa as well. More generally, it could be useful to have a European certification for infrastructures that takes into consideration quality standards (e.g., on open data rules).

Compliance with Open data principles

The compliance with open data rules affects also the shared data clouds.

A real anonymisation is not easy, sharing best practices and tools would help a lot. Sticking to the rules, it is not only about changing the names, it's more complex, and there are not many people with the right skills to deal with this. It might seem that a RI does not want to comply, but often what the legislation is asking is not feasible. Moreover, some rules are different in every country. It is possible to deal with GDPR and privacy but there is the need for people with the right skills to share knowledge, experiences and best practices across countries.

IPR issues

The difference between “service facility” and “collaborator” should be considered. In fact, an infrastructure could work as a service facility to analyse data that it does not own, then IPR discussion is not necessary. On the other hand, in some projects an infrastructure is a collaborator pushing the boundaries and then IP is necessary, because it is a contributor of the research project. That is where most of the things get stuck. This should be discussed at the beginning of a project and inserted in an agreement. During the discussion, it was also noted that an infrastructure that is a service provider should be included in a catalogue in order to be known as such within the Alliance.

Language

Language is still an issue even though many universities are already bi-lingual (i.e., use a local language and English). It is acceptable that the default language of all descriptions and documentation is English. On the other hand, institutions should take into consideration the

potential for offering language learning opportunities to enhance collaborations and promote the use of other languages.

Further reflections and ideas on other barriers not emergent during the mapping exercises

Following the new EU regulation about the diagnostic field and clinical research (e.g., In Vitro Diagnostic device labelling requirement: IVDR), if there is an IVD label available on the market for a certain diagnosis, then it is mandatory to use it. This represents a problem, because university hospitals develop new techniques to push the type of diagnostic done. For example, the Prieto test is used for genetic anomalies. This is considered better than the one available on the market. However, the university hospital would not be allowed to use this test again if there is not an IVD, which is what some RIs are trying to ascertain and establish now. Having an IVD exemption for academic hospitals could foster greater innovation.

Overview on barriers

Barriers discussed in the CH breakout rooms:

- Registration constraints, in particular in relation to openness of infrastructures and open data policies
- Legal constraints mainly related to IPR but also difficulties in implementing FAIR data principles related to accessibility and privacy and safety issues.
- Language barriers, underlining the need to promote physical mobility and staff exchange and the added value of getting in touch with other cultures.
- Limited capacities due to physical, technical and technological constraints, that could be overcome by sharing the costs and personnel of infrastructures by developing clear user-guides for RIs.
- The need for the academic and professional community to have more information about Una Europa's mission and activities in relation to RIs.
- The need to carry out systematic mapping initiatives (by updating the Una.Resin mapping exercise) to have a comprehensive overview of the Alliance's RIs.

Barriers discussed in the OH breakout rooms:

- Registration constraints, underlining the need to facilitate access through, for example, a clear workflow, online registration tools, webinars, a clear contact person for the RIs
- The clearance of ethical and privacy rights required to conduct experiments and valorise research results: this could be addressed for example through the involvement of ethical committees to assess the ethical impact of sharing RIs and the creation of transnational boards that could help solve cross-country legal problems
- Limited capacities due to physical, technical and technological constraints: this barrier could be addressed for example by prioritizing the users of RIs in case of excessive

request and by having a clear overview of other labs using the same technology that could have capacity.

- Compliance with quality standards, based on the definition of minimum standards for RIs: global standards could be taken as a benchmark and the Alliance should consider giving a label based on minimum standards.
- Compliance with Open data principles, underlining the need to have skilled personnel and the importance of sharing knowledge and best practices across countries.
- IPR issues, distinguishing the specific role of a RIs (service facility or collaborator in a research project) and defining agreements accordingly.
- Language barriers, underlining the need to offer language learning to personnel.
- Specific barriers related to In Vitro Diagnostic device labelling requirement were discussed.

2.2 Summary of the Open Research survey report and list of webinars

Open Research survey outcomes and recommendations

This report provides a mapping analysis of the Open Research activities in Una Europa institutions in 2022-23 among the eight institutions under Una.Resin funded by the Horizon 2020 (Society IBA-SwafS-support-1-2020 call) and supporting the Research and Innovation dimension of European Universities.

It is important to revisit the project objective to reemphasize the Open Research aspects in the Una.Resin project and reflect on the future potential road map on this topic. This project aims to contribute to the multidimensional fields of research and innovation in the areas of: (i) developing a common research and innovation agenda and action plan; (ii) sharing research infrastructures and resources; (iii) strengthening human capital. In addition, Una.Resin facilitated the implementation of transversal areas: mainstreaming of comprehensive Open Science practices, and embedding citizens and other non-academic actors in all stages of the R&I lifecycle.

The report strongly aligns with the Una Europa 2030 Strategy aimed at the creation of the “university of the future” by working towards a pan-European campus regarding location, ideas, knowledge, and values. Here, Open Research is situated at the common grounds in achieving this overall objective including responsibilities for communities, strong academic standards, and humanitarian ethos. By striving for the long-term goal, Una Europa 2030 strategy proposes six institutional priorities and seven thematic priorities, where open research activities are centrally placed to take a transversal approach to create societal impact, public engagement, and a contribution towards the European Higher Educational Area and European Research Area.

In other words, **Open Research activities serve as a common thread in the Alliance framework** where the R&I ecosystem is developed, research and data infrastructure are made open and shared, and human capital development strategies are developed taking account of various areas including career path development, performance assessment, employees’ well-being, engagement with society, and support for early-career researchers.

The report on Open Research Survey documents the process and outcome of the full steps taken to develop, analyse and summarize the findings of the survey. Starting from the definition of survey focus and target population, the report documents questionnaire development, data collection, response quality assurance, analysis, writing the report, and formulating a proposal for strategy. **The scope of the survey was to serve as direct inputs for the development of Una.Resin R&I strategies, action plans, and pilot actions.**

More specifically, these are: (i). administrative and technical characteristics of available research infrastructures and resources regarding Open Access publication and FAIR and Open data; (ii). opportunities and barriers sharing infrastructures across institutions and between researchers; (iii) best practices and mutual learning examples on Open Research policies, Open Research outputs related to researcher assessment criteria and citizen engagement.

Survey respondents were identified through the cluster members of each institution, serving as focal points, to reach out to relevant experts within the institution, and to respond to questionnaire items. The respondent group was diverse ranging from policymakers, research administrators, researchers, and research support staff engaged in Open Research related activities. The survey instrument, i.e., the questionnaire (in .doc format), included **five different sections**:

1. Open Research policies;
2. University-based internal infrastructure and resources underpinning: Open Research; Open Access publication; FAIR/Open Research Data;
3. University-used recommended external infrastructure underpinning Open Research; Open Access publication; FAIR/Open Research data;
4. Human capital;
5. Citizen science as an emerging field.

Each section in the report deals with these five areas and includes **recommendations arising from the analysis and numerous discussions** with cluster experts, WP members, and other Una Europa colleagues including representatives in the governance model. From the report, the following observations and conclusions are drawn from each section of the analysis.

Overall, Open Research activities are integrated into the Open Research policies at the institutional level. Institutional engagements in different domains of open research activities and services are generally found sufficient, although the level and scope differ across topics and institutions. Institutions diverge in maturity and their actual implementation and practices in each specific domain from open access repositories, FAIR data repositories, use of external infrastructures and principles behind, and to areas of best practices of policies, facilities, services, staff training, and incentives. The varied Open Research activities across institutions were expected given the institutional policy framework reflected by the different engagements of each institution concerning various networks: university alliances and EU Open Science-related networks (EOSC, Open AIRE), and national and regional networks in the area of open research. The report perceives this diversity as enriching and promising since knowledge transfer between Una Europa institutions can lead to new opportunities to collaboratively work as an alliance. Few specific areas of interest are identified in the survey. Here, Open Research experts are interested in **translating the survey results into mutual learning exercises**, developing **potentially joint strategic areas for action**, and **practical recommendations** that

can assist in further mainstreaming Open Research practices across the Alliance, and promoting this more concretely under Una.Futura.

The following bullet points summarize the findings of the survey, that were used for the recommendations proposed in Section 1:

- All institutions are committed to Open Research, but the **maturity across institutions and domains differs**. Overall, the **underlying barriers to implementing Open Research activities** are related to organisational aspects (e.g., human and financial resource commitments, different management models for service provisions, institutional-specific repositories) followed by legal and financial areas. It is also noted that different models exist for financial support for open-access publications.
- A strong consensus exists on **promoting open-access journals and platforms** that support free access to researchers and the general public.
- At the level of institutional infrastructures on publications, research data, and external use of infrastructure, **services and tools are both internally and externally available for publication repositories**, but much less for research data one. This is likely due to advanced services and tools for publication repositories readily available at an international level, whereas research data management has developed much attention recently where available services and tools are increasing dramatically.
- More specifically, **expertise is mostly available** on: the provisions for funding Open Access publishing; the functions, provisions, and workflows of institutional or disciplinary publication repositories on systems; expertise in setting up or using a data repository followed by a journal hosting system and Open Access university press and PID services. Also, the topics of sharing knowledge on Data Management Plan (DMP) writing tools related to specific metadata standards emerged as relevant. Additional topics for which institutions can provide support are: DMP writing, data management; competence development of data stewards; support for regulatory compliance in GDPR; integrity guidelines about SSH; interactions between university and the national/regional research & innovation actions.
- Most of the abovementioned areas are also in **high demand for an exchange of best practices or the set-up of mutual learning exercises**. Most universities want to know more about the conditions and benefits of being an ORCID member (specific integration to make the function of ORCID membership), followed by areas such as: the functions, provisions, and workflows for institutional or disciplinary publication repositories; information on Open Access university presses; secure systems for sensitive data; software allowing collaboration on active data; anonymising or pseudonymising data software; and conditions for sharing.
- Against this background, there is **lack of expertise within the Alliance in the large IT-component** domains where institutions claim strong needs. These are: connection to the

EOSC; development of integrated workflows to support good Research Data Management (RDM), such as connection between privacy registry, ethics clearance, and DMP; large volume computing; software for collaborating on active data; pseudonymising and anonymising data. Regarding data infrastructure, EOSC is acknowledged as very important by all institutions to follow their general principles in promoting open science principles, and in particular, supporting the consolidation of FAIR data principles.

- **The benefits of having mutual learning exercise topics** by institutions also included topics such as: organisation of RDM services; organisations' provision issues (e.g., better service provision to researchers and external users, experience sharing on implementing new services, workflows, policies, and practice); data sharing and publishing; and deliver organisation services at institutional level for an integrated support; effective operation on archive data repository and increased use of data deposit; support for DMP writing and customising online tools. In addition, there are broader issues emphasised such as: how to overcome cultural barriers to sharing data and scholarly communication; how to provide better services to the academic community and external users; communications strategies and resources on Open Science topics.
- Human capital-related areas in having mutual learning exercises are **rewards and incentives for open science** (i.e., use of bio sketch CV and use of Open Science metrics; professionalisation of data stewardship). The question arises to what extent Una Europa as an alliance can take up a role in the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (COARA).
- Not all items are in high demand, and this may be due to several reasons. Some features are well known and embedded already in their institutions, or topics are of lesser interest to the universities in the network, or they are considered too specific for being treated at the Una Europa network level. These are: information on preprint servers; the availability of discipline-specific metadata standards; interoperable technical formats.
- Regarding training areas for human capital development, most universities have dedicated staff to support researchers both concerning Open Access publications and Open Data. Institutions offer training for the adoption, implementation, and enhancement of Open Science practices. However, it was not clear on the target groups (i.e., whether that is for the institution as a whole, i.e., all students, researchers, and staff, or specifically). At least in terms of the developmental needs of Open Access for employees, the results indicate that specialised knowledge is required regarding **legal aspects (i.e., Intellectual Property, regulatory constraints), national and EU policies, specific rules of funding programmes, technical expertise, and managerial expertise**. The initial outlook is given in this report, but more in-depth understanding is needed.
- **Citizens' engagement activities** are still low ranked in the hierarchy of priorities, even though there is a dramatic increase in the interest of all institutions. Here, the "programme approach" (i.e., through a series of interconnected projects under common

objectives) is called for to engage researchers and to strengthen the research environment and the capacity for implementing citizen engagement components in research projects.

The survey report makes **recommendations for the transformation of the institutional framework of Una Europa institutions** through the integration of Open Research activities (i.e., transversal activities). There are two broad areas and corresponding actions that are identified for Una Europa actions:

1. Develop frameworks to promote the **mutual exchange of best practices and knowledge on services, tools, and facilities**. The framework consists of three actions:
 - Organise **joint training activities, promote physical mobility, provide platforms, and create awareness through promotional campaigns and events**: Promoting best practices can take the form of joint training activities and awareness-raising campaigns (e.g., Una Europa Open Research Day or training modules for Una Europa organise schools, Ph.D. programmes, Open Research Ambassadors/Champions, etc.). They can focus on basic principles relating to Open Research, including citizen engagement (methodologies), and be included in joint BA programme European Studies BA and Una Europa micro-credentials. Training formats can take the form of digital platforms (e.g., webinars) where technical advice and documentation can be shared amongst research (support) staff;
 - Physical mobility for researchers and research management support staff to give training on key principles of Open Research to these diverse target groups will improve skills and add to their current expertise;
 - Sharing guidelines, models, and tools among the research support staff, research managers, and researchers of Una Europa institutions could be much more promoted.
2. **Encourage and ensure implementation of Open Research principles** including citizen engagement where relevant in all Una Europa-funded and supported projects.

List of best practices: webinar series organised by the Open Research Cluster

The Open Research Cluster organised a series of webinars to promote the exchange of best practices. The webinars' details and abstracts are reported here.

1. Webinar held on the 6th of May 2022: **“How to provide Open Access without paying, African partners”**.

Abstract: The objective of the webinar was to learn good practices, share experiences, and stimulate discussions on Open Access publication. The discussion was formulated within the framework of Una.Resin's project objective of building a Research and Innovation eco-system by taking a systematic approach to enabling research collaboration. In this context, Open Access publication, one area of the open science 8 principles, is truly a vehicle to realise this objective. The webinar resulted in the gaining of different and broader views on the opportunities and challenges of open-access publication in the context of research collaboration in the transnational context. It was a wonderful opportunity to invite four African colleagues working in the area of health sciences (one of the focus areas of Una Europa) as the Alliance aims to extend research collaboration with African institutions. This opportunity provides a first introduction not only to open science activities but also to create synergies in the research collaboration on the focus area (One Health, data science, etc.).

2. Webinar held on the 16th of September 2022: **“Sharing KU Leuven research data repositories (RDR) practices”**. It included two parts: (i) implementation of an institutional research data repository to enable FAIR data publication; (ii) Data management plan (DMP) submission and review via the DMP-Monitoring Tool.

Abstract part 1: In January 2022, KU Leuven launched its new institutional research data repository, KU Leuven RDR. The platform is tailor-made for the needs of KU Leuven researchers and the wants of the European and Flemish governing bodies for the publication and preservation of finished research data. While keeping these needs and wants in mind, KU Leuven RDR also makes sure to offer the data openly where possible and supply the metadata in standardised formats such as Dublin Core, DDI, OpenAire and others. This together with the OAI-PMH harvesting infrastructure makes the published data's metadata findable, interoperable and machine-readable. On top of a platform to publish research data, we have also worked on integrating our other LIBIS library systems by providing custom look-ups in the literature repository for related publications to the dataset, by providing a look-up for KU Leuven authors, creating a dataset claimer for externally published research dataset, and enabling automatic linking and registration of datasets in the literature repository. All of this is aimed at publishing research data in a Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) way to lower the cost of research and improve verifiability and reproducibility of research results. The idea of FAIR data publication is to publish your data as 'open as possible, but as closed as necessary' and is as such an important part of Open Science best practices and a vehicle for collaborative research, as research data is made accessible and available for the re-use and validation of research results. In this presentation we will give a brief overview of the implementation trajectory of our institutional research data repository, an overview of the infrastructure and its many integrations with internal and external systems, and the lessons learned and work ahead. We finish with some ideas on future collaboration on repositories within the Una Europa and Una.Resin context as food for discussion with the participants.

Abstract part 2: Writing a data management plan (DMP) is considered good practice and many funders request a DMP. For most projects financed by a Flemish funder, an initial DMP has to be submitted to the research coordination office of the researcher's university. This year we received over 600 initial DMPs and this number is still growing. To process these DMPs, including the reporting to the funder and providing feedback to the researcher, we built a DMP monitoring tool. At the start of the project a folder is generated and the researcher gets an email with link to the folder, guidance and the headline, and reminders follow if needed. The DMPs are reviewed by a team of RDM support staff. In the tool we assign a main reviewer who can forward the DMP to colleagues with expertise in a specific domain. We check if all questions are sufficiently addressed, give tips on how to improve RDM practices, and we learn which areas to focus on in our next RDM training sessions. Our feedback supports preparation for the final DMP, which is part of the final report, and is archived as part of the tool together with the DMP so the researcher can easily find this during the research or when preparing the final DMP (which forms part of the final report).

3. Webinar held on the 28th of October 2022, “**UCM Scientific Production Portal, a patron-oriented service**”

Abstract: UCM Scientific Production Portal, a patron-oriented service The UCM Scientific Production Portal is a service designed to disseminate the outcomes of the institution's research activity, like any other CRIS services. Providing a user-friendly environment adapted to the needs and requirements of patrons is essential for its success. The Dialnet Foundation is a reference entity in Spain for the creation of valuable content for the academic community. The relationship between UCM and Dialnet began with the collaboration in the project to create the bibliographic portal of academic scientific literature in Spain, Dialnet. Subsequently, the Dialnet Foundation launched Dialnet Métricas, a project that UCM actively promotes with the aim of generating a portal of scientific production indicators. The latest addition to the Dialnet ecosystem is the Scientific Production Portal, in which the Foundation provides an integrated tool for the development of an institutional CRIS (Current Research Information System), a basic infrastructure for the communication and dissemination of the results of the institution's scientific activity. Throughout years of collaboration, the Dialnet Foundation is a strategic partner for UCM in the design of research support services. The UCM Scientific Production Portal facilitates access to publications and research data and supports faculty and researchers in the processes of evaluation and impact of their research. Moreover, the Portal is also a basic pillar in the promotion of open science policies from our institution: it improves the reproducibility of research, shows the relationship between public funding of research and its outcomes, and supports the governmental bodies about scientific activity. The information provided by the Portal gives visibility to the University's open access production and serves as a reference to measure the scope of institutional policies.

4. The webinar held on the 13th of December 2022 included two presentations:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017416.

“Excellent, Satisfactory or Poor - Introducing Finnish DMP evaluation guidance”

Abstract: The presentation covered various areas including the historical background of the Finnish DMP template and guidance since 2018, the process in setting up a working group for the evaluation of guidance taking account of documentation, metadata ethical, and legal compliance, and opening, publishing and archiving data; evaluation guidance for self-assessment purposes. More information: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4762326>

“Data management policy (DMPol) template for research infrastructures”

Abstract: The presentation covered the data management policy in University of Helsinki introducing the DMP template that was created by Academy of Finland and Tuuli Office integrating views of support services of research infrastructure (RI) and data. The template was shared in detail, covering: general description of data managed within research infrastructure, opening and restricted sharing of data, documentation and metadata, storage, back-up, and access control data. More information: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3690865>

5. Webinar held on the 22nd of March 2023 “Open Research activities in JU: how to share repositories within 6 universities in Poland”.

This lecture has covered a wide range of topics on Open Research activities giving an overview from Jagiellonian University including:

1. Open Access publication repository at the Jagiellonian University - [Jagiellonian University Repository](#)
2. Open Access Policy
3. Open Research Data Repository of Cracow Universities (RODBUK is co-created by six Krakow universities: Jagiellonian University, AGH University of Science and Technology, Cracow University of Technology, Pedagogical University of Krakow, University of Physical Education in Krakow, Krakow University of Economics).
4. Data Stewards at the Jagiellonian University

Abstract: During the webinar, experiences related to the implementation of open science at the Jagiellonian University will be presented. The activities discussed will focus on both the historical aspect of the implementation of Open Science and the current activities. The following will be presented: the open access policy adopted at the Jagiellonian University, the Jagiellonian University Repository, whose main goal is to promote the publishing achievements of researchers, the Open Research Data Repository created by six Krakow universities (Jagiellonian University, AGH University of Science and Technology, Cracow University of Technology, Pedagogical University of Krakow, University of Physical Education in Krakow, Krakow University of Economics), and the scope of activity of Data Stewards at the Jagiellonian University.

6. Webinar held on the 27th of April 2023: **“Interdisciplinary culture of collaboration and Multilingualism, FUB”**.

Abstract: We want to take up two specific aspects from UNESCO's Open Science definition in our webinar: "make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone" and "increase scientific collaborations" (UNESCO (2021) Recommendation on Open Science. <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMMH8546>) with a focus on digital humanities.

Two talks were delivered:

“Shaping the digital transformation critically: the ‘Ada Lovelace Centre for Digital Humanities’ at Freie Universität Berlin”

The digital transformation of the humanities is no short-lived trend. Through ubiquitous access to knowledge, through networked and increasingly digitised archives, through disruptive innovations in artificial intelligence, and through new technologies for processing and storing ever-growing amounts of data, research in the humanities is undergoing intense changes. Next to the development of trustworthy and appropriate digital infrastructures, the active and critical design of this transformation in research and teaching requires the creation of open spaces of encounter between at times radically different research cultures. The "Ada Lovelace Centre for Digital Humanities (ADA)" is set out to establish an interdisciplinary culture of collaboration in the humanities. The talk presents the concept and the formats of the ADA.

"Disrupting Digital Monolingualism": Enabling Multilingual Research and Infrastructures

Although multilingualism is a constitutive factor of research, teaching, learning, and working in academic institutions, academic knowledge infrastructures can fall short on supporting more than the use of the English language and Latin scripts. Under the motto "Disrupting Digital Monolingualism" (King's College 2020), more and more digital humanists and librarians are collaborating in order to address this Anglophone hegemony as a cause for cultural and technological/digital asymmetries as well as a barrier to global scholarly exchange in general (e.g., lack of visibility/accessibility of and access to research or sources in non-Anglophone languages and non-Latin scripts). The talk aims at raising awareness of multilingual issues and research infrastructures with a special focus on Digital Humanities and non-Latin scripts. With the example of the "Multilingual DH Lab" in the ADA, it introduces stakeholders and networks within & beyond FUB. Thus, the talk also strives to instigate a discussion on multilingualism within the Una.Resin network.

7. The webinar was held on the 16th of May 2023 **“Open Research as a Tool for Addressing Global Challenges”** as part of UoE conference

Abstract (available at this link: [Submissions | Edinburgh Open Research](#)): Open Research (OR) cannot in itself solve any of the huge problems that face the world, but what role can it play in making our responses to them more effective, and ensure that everyone is able to benefit from advances in research? That is the question we hope to address in this conference

by bringing together researchers who apply OR principles to their work with those who would like to do so. This list of possible topics are simply suggestions and are not exhaustive:

- How can the adoption of Open Research practices help in the global battle against climate change, or in combatting future pandemics?
- Does OR have a role to play in improving equality and diversity within research?
- Can it support efforts to decolonise research and ensure equitable access to research outputs?
- How can we ensure that researchers at any stage in their career are recognized and rewarded for being open and transparent?
- How can we increase public participation in research?
- Who owns the data? Knowledge justice and data ownership in Citizen Science.

8. Webinar held on the 22nd of May 2023 **"Open Digital Archives and a new AI-assisted Tool for Mapping Current Research. Recent Experiences & Perspectives at UP1 - Panthéon-Sorbonne"**.

Abstract: Our talk will present the French National open archives “HAL” and their use in mapping current research at Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne. In the first part, we will present the open archives “HAL” and their implementation at our institution, focusing especially on the role of the University Libraries in promoting their use and in structuring a diffuse network of contact persons. In the second part of the talk, we will present a recent “proof of concept” project, which uses the open archives’ metadata as the basis for an Expert Finder System. This tool deploys artificial intelligence (namely the Large Language Models “BERT” and “GPT-3”) to identify experts on a given subject within our research community.

2.3 Report on the joint workshop with the RiTrainPlus project

Introduction

On the 10th and 11th of October 2022, the **Collaborative Workshop** hosted by the WP2 of the RiTrain Plus project was held at UNIBO, in Bologna.

The workshop was an important occasion for **networking** and allowed a constructive **discussion between representatives of various institutions involved in the RiTrain Plus and Una.Resin projects.**

Representatives of both projects presented the results achieved in the tasks so far completed. The research conducted confirmed the urgent **need for a training programme to prepare future managers of research infrastructures and for a continuing training of those who are already holding such positions.** In order to accomplish this objective, collaboration between universities, research centres and every other possible stakeholder involved is essential, given the inter-connection between them.

According to the objectives of RiTrain Plus WP2, the urge to develop and introduce theoretical and practical teachings for managerial skills, throughout the entire university career (Bachelor, Master and PhD) was highlighted. Moreover, it was underlined the need for the universities' governance to understand the importance of these courses in order to include them in the training programme in their institutions.

During the workshop, group work was carried out to identify the presence in universities of courses on the topics identified as strategic by Task 2.1 of RiTrain Plus. It emerged that although there are existing courses with compatible learning outcomes, there is a lack of opportunities available, and an urge for a more structured approach. Participants discussed possible ways to integrate existing courses and to develop new ones by realising training paths, possibly widespread across universities, providing students with the opportunity to acquire credits in different institutions through distance learning or mobility programmes.

This purpose, as already suggested in RiTrain Plus proposal, could be fulfilled through the use of **micro-credentials**. Nevertheless, this flexible tool, in order to gain efficiency, will require a wide support from the highest number of university and institutions, in addition to a clear regulation and accreditation process. This proposal was appreciated by the representatives of Una Europa who suggested to officially present it to the Board of Directors and Research Strategy Group meeting (November 2022).

In addition to the **importance of training a new generation of RIs managers**, the workshop discussed the **activity of mapping research infrastructures across Europe**. It was reiterated that there is a need to create a strong network between existing infrastructures that will allow the realisation of the open science and open research area, pursuing the objectives of efficiency

and sustainability. Exchanges of best practices between countries should also be further implemented, encouraging and ensuring mobility of students and professionals. The activities carried out during the implementation of the Una.Resin project, especially by WP2 on “Research Infrastructures and Resources” were analyzed and possible pathways for the future were discussed.

The event was highly appreciated by the participants and the new ideas and connections made will serve a powerful resource for future collaboration and for advancing in the objectives of both projects. The agenda and key takeaways are presented below.

Agenda

Day 1 - Oct 10th 2022	
13:00-14:00	Arrival & Lunch
<i>The two projects: Results presentation</i>	
14:00-14:30	The RiTrainPlus vision
14:30-15:00	The Una.Resin vision
15:00-15:20	RiTrainPlus D2.1 results Identifying and Updating Training needs in European Research Infrastructures and Core Facilities
15:20-15:40	Una.Resin D2.1 results Research Infrastructures and Resources: Mapping, Strategy and Pilot Actions
15:40-16:00	Coffee Break
<i>Co-creation of the Learning Activities</i>	
16:00-17:45	Group work on IRs and CF world

17:45-18:00	Wrap-up of the day
20:30	Workshop Dinner – Ristorante “ La Scalinatella ” - Via Caduti di Cefalonia, 5/e, 40125 Bologna BO

Day 2 - Oct 11th 2022	
Universities engagement	
9:00 – 9:30	A strategic vision for coordinated training actions and for a European School for Management of Research Infrastructures (ESMRI)
9:30 - 9:50	Research Infrastructure and Core Facilities in Finland
9:50 – 10:20	Digital micro credential system
10:20-10:40	The role of Universities' alliance and associations in the mutual recognition of ECTS
10:40 - 11:00	Coffee Break
11:00 - 12:00	List of future actions and wrap-up of the day

Key takeaways

The RiTrainPlus vision and WP2 results

- There is a strong need for collaboration between RIs and Universities: they are autonomous entities that have to cooperate for a common goal
- The major goal is the exchange of personnel, resources and instruments
- It is important that career paths and professional roles needed inside the RIs and CFs are made known since the bachelor level
- Elimination of bias in communication regarding the research field is a priority

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017416.

- Una Europa can have a great impact creating a commitment within universities in introducing Learning Activities embedded in existing courses and promoting a Longitudinal Learning Path on managerial skills.
- Strategic synergies between RiTrain Plus project and the future follow up to Una.Resin project could be created, working on complementary actions
- The important results of Task 2.1 were presented, highlighting the training needs of European Research Infrastructures
- The methodology of the study was illustrated to the participants outside RiTrain team, in particular 2 aspects were described: a quantitative online survey among 330 members of RIs and CFs was combined with 17 qualitative guided interviews among managers from eight structurally selected countries; the motivation and doxa of RI and CFs managers from different fields were analysed
- Seven skills were identified as necessary:
 - communication and engagement
 - leadership and staff management
 - positioning in the scientific community
 - academic excellence & broad and deep academic understanding for the field
 - project management & organization management
 - deeper knowledge about the field of science and research in Europe
 - communication skills on different levels

The Una.Resin vision and WP2 results

- The objective of the Project Una.Resin is the creation of a common barrier-free R&I eco-system across the Una Europa Alliance
- This goal can be achieved by taking the first steps towards the sharing of research strengths, infrastructure and resources
- In this framework, it is also important to develop a vision of common research culture
- An important dimension of the project is the involvement involving citizens and non-academic actors across all regions of our eco-system (Open research)
- Collaborating with other European University Alliances, sharing experiences and learning from each other is also paramount
- Six Clusters of experts support the project activities: Research Coordination, Research Infrastructure, Research Career and Culture, Open Research, Citizen Engagement, Public Private and Third Sector
- New fundings for the future need to be guaranteed: the new Erasmus+ project Una Futura is a possibility
- Speakers illustrated the WPs of Una.Resin towards a common R&I eco-system with a special focus on the objectives, methodology and results of WP2 on Sharing Research Infrastructures and Resources /RIs)

- The methodology followed three important steps:
 - A threefold mapping exercise: thematic mapping of RIs in the fields of Cultural Heritage and One Health; mapping and analysis of RIs policies; and organisational, managerial funding models
 - Development of a shared Strategy and Action Plan for sharing RIs, also based on a co-creation workshop with stakeholders
 - Co-design of pilot actions experimenting concrete formats to share and open RIs
- The importance of engaging a wide community of stakeholders in order to create a common space of knowledge, tools and practices exchange was highlighted
- The main barriers to sharing of RIs according to the area were presented
- The results of the co-creation workshop were illustrated, including the solution to the main barriers
- Pilot actions will be the creation of a blueprint of a common RIs catalogue and the creation of a networks of RIs aimed to promote matchmaking, community building and collaboration towards opening and sharing RIs across the alliance.

Group work results

- The group work focused on the 6 Learning Activities that were addressed by the WP2 of RiTrain Plus as essential to train future managers of RIs. The participants were asked to evaluate whether the activities were in any form present in their universities, which were or should be the Learning Outcomes of each LA and the number of ECTS needed to fulfil them.
- Various answers were given but what primarily emerged was:
 - a general lack of the needed activities
 - the presence of some courses eligible to include the addressed LAs
 - the urge for a deeper investigation within the represented universities
- The participants agreed the following:
 - to maintain the courses in a mixed mode (virtual and in presence)
 - to offer them in English (in order for students to get used to the international environment from the BA programme)
 - that everyone should explore their institution's readiness to host new courses centred on the pre-designed LAs
- It was requested to the workshop participants to keep up the good collaboration and research within their own institutions, and to present to the institutional decision-makers and boards the idea to introduce the abovementioned courses.

Universities engagement

- The coordinator of the RiTrain Plus project highlighted the widely recognised urgency to create an integrated a path to educate the Research Infrastructures' managers of the future.
- Through the first edition of the European project RiTrain Plus, an Executive Master in Management of Research Infrastructures (EMMRI) was developed which has proved very useful for professionals of the field. Thanks to the experience gained from the EMMRI master and the many years of field experience of the participants, RitrainPlus will be able to offer a better and more comprehensive training experience.
- The Research Infrastructure development plans of University of Helsinki - through its participation in the ESFRI roadmap and its strategic role in Finland - was presented.
- The complete map of the financing plan of the RIs, followed by an insight on investments on lifecycle planning in order to promote a sustainable development of RIs. At UH the establishment of the economic sustainability of the infrastructures is based on the adoption of an open but not free of charge access.
- It was underlined that RIs are also places in which users can apprehend practices related to open science following the guide principle "as open as possible as closed as necessary".
- The goals of the Una Europa Alliance and the objectives for the future were presented:
 - designing the university of the future
 - attracting external funding opportunities for the association
 - creating an impact on universities' education, research and services to society
- The collaboration between the partner universities in different fields are designing Joint European degrees, joint doctoral programme and Micro-Credentials as a tool for flexible learning pathways.
- The plan of the Alliance will be the creation of an Inter-University Campus creating opportunities of virtual mobility and community building.
- Through the sequence of projects (1Europe and Una.Resin) the pathway for an Una Europa roll-out project has been prepared with the aim of involving a broader group of participants, strengthening the core values of European universities and developing the most innovative educational programme.
- The possibility for Una Europa to collaborate with RiTrain Plus will be discussed with the Board of Directors and Research Strategy Group: a representative of RiTrain Plus will be invited to attend the meeting and explain the project objectives and possible synergies with Una Europa activities.

Conclusion of the workshop

- The participants were required to disseminate inside their institutions the information acquired during the workshop

- A proposal on micro-credentials and Learning Activities (with their Learning Outcomes) will be defined and presented to the BoD of Una Europa⁶ in order to promote the RiTrain Task 2.2 goals inside the Alliance
- The objective of WP5, i.e., the creation of the European School for Managers of Research Infrastructures (ESMRI), created on the model of the European University Institute (EUI), will further be discussed in the workshop of May

⁶ A representative of RiTrain Plus WP2 was invited to the BoD and RSG meetings in November 2022 (in Leuven) and in June 2023 (in Leiden) to present opportunities for joint collaboration.

2.4 Pilot actions for sharing RIs: concept, format, evaluation methodology and preliminary results

The context

In a context with rapid transitions and immense challenges to face, creating a sustainable, locally embedded, and globally articulated ecosystem of universities is more urgently needed than ever. Societal challenges that accelerated during the pandemic pushed the demand of responsibilities and visions of universities even more. Alliances of European Universities are committed to responding to this changing context and its manifold socio-economic, environmental, and technological challenges.

RIs prove to be instrumental for meeting these challenges. As stated in the *Brno Declaration on Fostering Global Ecosystem of Research Infrastructures* (2022) RIs “bring together a critical mass of human, material and financial resources, and integrate a large variety of stakeholders, including outside R&I, in a multi-disciplinary and cross-sectorial way”, and thus “facilitate problem-solving and solution-oriented approaches” that are key to tackling grand societal challenges. Research Infrastructures are indeed strongly embedded in the practices and experience of research, as engines for research data generation, knowledge elaboration, as well as education and training. RIs thus play a fundamental role in the advancement of knowledge and technology and in achieving wider societal impacts. They also contribute to regional, national, European, and global development and can be considered as one of the most important facilitators of international cooperation in science.

To support the development (i.e., establishment, operationalisation, upscaling) of RIs at the European level, important efforts are made by EU countries and research communities to stay aligned with the ERA framework, and in particular with the ESFRI, national, and regional roadmaps, while adapting EU specificities to local contexts.

Within Una.Resin, sharing RIs is a key pillar to moving towards a barrier-free common R&I ecosystem. RIs are indeed key enablers of research and technological innovation and are also pivotal in training researchers and facilitating collaborations across disciplines and sectors. A vast range of infrastructures, from small-medium sized individual RIs to large-scale ESFRI initiatives, are present in each Una institution. This diversity across Una Europa institutions is a strength, which calls for more synergies, collaborations, and visibility. Pooling this vast constellation of large-scale, small and medium-sized RIs by encouraging joint cooperation is necessary for several reasons.

Firstly, providing support to small and medium-sized RIs, as they are usually deeply rooted and well-integrated in their local substrate, will ensure engagements of a wide community of stakeholders across all disciplinary fields. This position aligns with one of the Una Resin’s

project objectives in involving citizens and non-academic actors (business, NGOs) across all regions of our Una Europa eco-system.

Secondly, this will also allow the multiple interconnections that already exist between ESFRI initiatives or national roadmap of Research Infrastructures, and smaller-scale RIs to be reinforced and expanded. This is likely to increase and facilitate knowledge transfer between RIs with different experiences. Strengthening the RIs ecosystem at that level will certainly open new routes of collaboration and, thereby, enhance our competitiveness as a university alliance at European and international scales.

Thirdly, small and medium-sized RIs are confronted with a severe lack of EU funding, since most of the EU funds available for RIs to Una Europa institutions are targeted towards larger scale infrastructures and often concentrated on initial set up funds. Una Europa support has a pivotal role in this regard: by creating a common space for exchange of knowledge, tools, and practices and by offering ramp-up funding (if feasible), accelerating the paths towards opening and sharing RIs.

Work delivered by WP2: from the mapping exercise to the co-creation with stakeholders

In the first stage of the project, WP2 activities focused on a threefold mapping exercise: (i) benchmarking Una Europa member universities' RIs strategies, policies, initiatives, as well as organisational and funding models; (ii) mapping of the RIs related to the challenge "Exploring cultural heritage to strengthen inclusion and participative communities" (Cultural Heritage); (iii) mapping of the RIs related to the challenge "Promoting the wellbeing of human and animals in a sustainable and healthy environment" (One Health).

A further step was the organization of a co-creation workshop aimed at collecting the ideas and inputs of the academic and professional community for the development of an Una Europa strategy and action plan for sharing research infrastructures. During the co-creation workshop, the main results obtained during the first year were discussed with RI managers and researchers of all Una Europa universities, including members of the Research Infrastructure Cluster and of the Self-Steering Committees of the two focus areas involved (i.e., Cultural Heritage and One Health). The discussion was structured around four main drivers (principles for sharing RIs; funding needs; skills and knowledge; barriers to share RIs) and allowed WP2 team to collect also inputs and initial ideas for developing the pilot actions.

The inputs emerged during the workshop were used to identify the preliminary drivers of the strategy for sharing RIs, that were subsequently revised:

1. Defining **common guiding principles for sharing RIs** that could be agreed upon and adopted by Una Europa universities.
2. Identification of **funding opportunities** related to RIs.

3. Definition of a **training** plan for researchers, managers, technical personnel of RIs on relevant topics (e.g., management, communication/dissemination) and mutual learning initiatives (e.g., mobility, webinars) aimed at improving the skills related to RIs across Una Europa universities.
4. Definition of **matchmaking processes and tools** that will include the facilitation of matchmaking initiatives and the blueprint for the creation of a tool (common catalogue and platform of services) to exchange information about the RIs available across Una Europa universities, as well as opportunities and knowledge.

The pilot actions proposed by WP2 and described in this document are related to the strategic drivers that emerged from WP2 activities.

Implementation methodology

WP2 pilot actions are aimed at exploring **concrete formats** for opening and sharing RIs within Una Europa, in particular in the fields of **One Health** and **Cultural Heritage**, the Focus Areas which have been thematically selected as case studies. They will be focused on actions that make use of the strengths of the Una Europa universities. As emerged from the mapping exercise and from the co-creation workshop, matchmaking is key.

As it was described above, both WP2 pilot actions are connected to the need of promoting matchmaking and networking among RIs across the Alliance. The first pilot action will facilitate the matchmaking by developing a blueprint and a first prototype of a **tool** that can be used to promote awareness about the RIs available across Una Europa universities. The second pilot action will develop a format for enabling matchmaking and networking of **people** involved in RIs management, contributing to community building around RIs in the R&I ecosystem of Una Europa universities.

Pilot Action 1: Develop a blueprint of a Una Europa RIs catalogue

The **aim** of the first pilot action is to develop a blueprint of a common catalogue of RIs. The catalogue will be based on a process to harvest the existing information on Una Europa RIs. If feasible, a first prototype of a harvesting tool will be developed. For the universities that have not developed a catalogue of RIs, the blueprint will provide guidelines and indications on how to create it.

The main **benefits** of a prospective common catalogue are the following ones:

- to increase awareness by the academic community about the RIs available across the Una Europa universities;
- to promote R&I cooperation and an efficient use of RIs;
- to connect RIs sharing and promotion of Open Science;
- to promote the RIs towards possible non-academic public, private, and third sector users or customers and also towards citizens.

The first step of this pilot action foresees the preparation of an overview table with the basic information on the tools available within Una.Resin universities.

WP2 team will organise meetings with the IT staff involved in the RIs tool of each university. WP2 lead will promote the meeting, proposing a possible process to create a prototype tool and illustrating the steps needed to achieve the creation of a common catalogue. This proposal will be discussed by IT experts of all the universities involved; tools and solutions adopted by other universities or alliances will be taken into consideration during the discussion. RI Cluster members and Una.Resin project managers will be invited to participate.

The final **output** of the workshops will be the first **draft of the blueprint**⁷ for a common RIs catalogue at Una Europa level. The draft will be circulated for comments and revisions and then finalised.

Pilot Action 2 Matchmaking formats to improve the Una Europa RIs sharing

The **aim** of the second pilot action is to develop matchmaking and networking formats targeted to the professional and academic communities from the two thematic fields (Cultural Heritage and One Health) involved in WP2. The proposed format will bring together academics and technicians of Una Europa RIs to discuss possible paths for sharing infrastructures. The pilot action will test matchmaking processes through specific case studies, with a view to developing scalable formats. The lessons learnt will be of interest for RIs of different types and in different thematic fields.

The main **benefits** of the matchmaking formats are the following ones:

- to stimulate networking among the Una Europa RIs;
- to exchange practices and knowledge;
- to foster R&I collaborations and efficient use of RIs;
- to enhance RIs visibility within the Alliance as well as towards external actors and potential users.

The first step of this pilot action is the definition of the **scope** for each thematic field (CH and OH) (e.g., theme, type of RIs, type of technology, etc.) in agreement with the SSCs. Based on the selected scope, WP2 team - in collaboration with the Research Infrastructure Cluster and SSCs - will identify the **relevant RIs** that could be involved; the starting point will be the list of infrastructures that participated in the mapping exercise (thematic mapping in the OH and CH fields) and the ones that participated in the co-creation workshop. In addition, the Una.Resin Project Managers, the members of the Research Infrastructure Cluster and the SSCs Cultural Heritage and One Health will be consulted to identify more RIs that could be potentially interested in joining the pilot process.

⁷ In the paragraph “Preliminary results” of this section the executive summary of the Blueprint is included. The complete Blueprint will be made available with the framework of evaluation of the pilot action.

A **call for expression of interest** will be launched targeting the relevant group of RIs representatives (academics and technicians). A specific form will be used to preliminarily collect the needs, interests and basic information that will be used to shape the workshops. The form will include a section to understand what the participants expect and how the engagement in the matchmaking process can meet their needs. For each case study the following process will be put in place:

- The group of RIs that expressed interest will be invited to attend matchmaking workshops aimed at reflecting on possible paths for opening/sharing RIs. During the workshops, the participants will discuss: mutual interests; how to exchange knowledge and expertise; how to move concretely towards opening/sharing infrastructures; how to foster collaboration within the RIs network. The workshop's agenda will start with the mutual knowledge of participants, which will be asked to share experiences and knowledge related to the RIs that they represent.
- A Miro board or a canvas will be used as a tool to facilitate the discussion on the reported needs and interests and to collect possible new ideas on paths towards opening/sharing coming up from the discussion.
- The participants will discuss about which activities could be undertaken taking into consideration possible barriers and how to overcome them.
- The activities could be structured in an action plan/roadmap for undertaking concrete actions to move towards opening/sharing RIs.

Following up on the outcomes of the first meeting, other meetings will be organised to complete the whole process. The WP2 team will support the organisation of all meetings and the production of the output. Relevant experts from RI Cluster (and, where relevant from the other Clusters) and SSCs will also be invited to participate.

The final **output** of each pilot will be a report⁸ with the key takeaways, describing the ideas that emerged from the case study, i.e., the specific actions that the groupings of RIs will undertake to move towards opening and sharing their infrastructures. The outputs of the different case studies will also lead to more general recommendations aimed at ensuring the scalability of the pilot format, that will be widely disseminated for the uptake of other Una Europa RIs.

Evaluation methodology

A **framework for the evaluation** of the pilot project was defined by the project coordinator with the inputs of all partners. WP2 team will address the evaluation framework providing

⁸ In the paragraph "Preliminary results" of this section, the reports of the pilot actions carried out in the field of CH and OH are included. The reports will be also made available with the framework of the evaluation of the pilot action.

quantitative and qualitative data related to the participation of Una Europa universities' representatives in the two pilot actions that were carried out.

The framework for evaluating pilot actions foresees the following fields:

1.1 Purpose and scope of evaluation

The purpose of the evaluation is to assess progress to date following the implementation of the pilot projects and understand the extent to which Una.Resin has achieved what it set out to do. It also serves to further identify areas of best practices and lessons learned to carry forward in any future iterations of Una Europa projects, for example in Una.Futura. The review seeks to draw out learnings from the pilot projects and understand what worked well and why, what challenges were faced and how these were overcome, and whether there are opportunities for improvements in future implementations.

2.1 Evaluation Questions

This pilot evaluation will explore a set of questions covering the following criteria: objectives and aims of the pilot; considerations on the initial design and implementation processes; outcomes and impact of the project; and sustainability.

2.2 Objectives and aims of the pilot

- i. Outline the specific Transformation Module(s) and any sub-themes that the pilot aimed to address.
- ii. What barriers to cross border and cross-sectoral research and innovation collaboration did the project address?
- iii. To what extent has the pilot project addressed the Transformation Modules (TMs) towards the desired institutional change?
- iv. Indicate any lessons that were explored or drawn from other Una.Resin or related projects in the implementation of this pilot?

2.3 Initial design and implementation of the pilot project

- i. Describe the design of the pilot project considering alignments with the overall Una.Resin project objectives (internal) and other Una Europa and/or European University Alliance interventions (external).
- ii. Describe the various sources of data collected and the analysis undertaken. Take into consideration the framework used for gathering and including feedback from your stakeholders.
- iii. Considering the design and implementation phases, describe the roles of the Clusters and/or Self-Steering Committees in the delivery of the pilot?
- iv. What challenges were faced during the design and implementation phases of this project and how they were overcome or how you intend to tackle?

2.4 Outcomes and Impact of the pilot project

- i. Discuss the key outcomes and impact of the pilot project including any institutional change actions identified.
- ii. How have these outcomes/impact addressed the initial aims including enabling barrier-free collaboration in research and innovation?
- iii. To what extent has the pilot project been able to translate and synthesise Una.Resin knowledge and innovations into accessible formats?
- iv. To what extent has the outcomes of the pilot project (if any) been taken up and/or influenced decision-makers at the various levels – institutional, national, EU (European Union)? Or what institutional, national and EU decisions could be influenced in the future based on this pilot?

2.5 Sustainability of the pilot project

- i. How, when, and under what conditions will the insights and outcomes delivered through the pilot project be replicated/scaled up or continued?
- ii. How do you intend to scale up this project after the end of the programme/program/programme
- iii. What has been the cost-benefits analyses of the pilot actions? Elaborate on recommendations to national and European policy on the way forward.

2.6 Lessons learned

- i. Highlight the key lessons learned (5 max) as a result of the delivery of this project (200-words max).

2.7 Recommendation for the future

- i. Suggest recommendations (5 max) on how this project can be scaled up (200-words max).

2.1 Please include any pilot specific free text that is not covered above

Preliminary results

Pilot action 1 - “Blueprint for a common catalogue of research infrastructures”

The blueprint provides the relevant information to develop and implement a common digital catalogue of research infrastructures within the Una Europa Alliance. The catalogue is intended as a collection of data about research infrastructures aimed at facilitating the process of sharing and opening the research infrastructures within the Alliance. The blueprint foresees the inclusion of both the basic information of the RI and of the RI’s manager or responsible researchers but also other information like the research results produced from the use of

research infrastructure and services such as booking and training. Making this information available to the Una Europa community offers possible paths for opening and sharing the research infrastructures within the Alliance.

The need for such a catalogue of research infrastructures is based on the idea that the first step to establish any kind of collaboration is to be aware of the available infrastructures. The academic community engaged during the implementation of Una.Resin confirmed that their expectations about Una Europa is to network with infrastructures belonging to the other universities. They believe that a catalogue could support the development of the networks and, therefore, to improve their research and identify additional possibilities on research collaboration. During the co-creation workshop implemented in June 2022, the researchers and RIs managers/experts showed great interest in getting to know each other. This element was considered as crucial and is therefore also proposed as one of the activities under the three pillars described in Section 1, specifically under Pillar 1 “Promoting openness of RIs and data infrastructures to foster research collaboration”.

The **main benefits of the catalogue** are the following: (i) increase awareness for the academic community about the RIs available across the Una Europa universities and facilitate access to them; (ii) promote R&I cooperation and an efficient use of RIs; (iii) connect RIs and promote Open Science principles in their operation and activities; (iv) promote the RIs towards possible non-academic public, private, and third sector users and also towards citizens; (v) improve the economic sustainability of the infrastructure.

The content of the blueprint is the result of the pilot action organised by WP2 of Una.Resin project. IT experts from the universities were engaged in four workshops from December 2022 to May 2023. During these workshops, they were involved in discussions about previous experiences in digital catalogues of infrastructures and planning of the Una Europa common catalogue.

The inputs emerged from the discussions held during the pilot action were collected and organised in the blueprint as different chapters.

The first chapter focuses on catalogues of infrastructures in the Una Europa universities to report the current situation at Alliance level and designing the common catalogue starting from the **resources already available at institutional level**. The catalogues of Freie Universität Berlin, KU Leuven, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, University of Edinburgh, and University of Helsinki are described.

The second chapter is dedicated to the **best practices** of catalogues that involve universities of the Alliance: FRIS - Flanders Research Information Space, the booking and accounting tool OpenIRIS at FU Berlin, and in the Berlin University Alliance (BUA), Research infrastructure development at UH. The results presented offer a scaled perspective of what the common catalogue can represent transnationally. The blueprint considers also the issues related to the increasing number of partners and the impact on the management of the catalogue.

The third chapter reports the **lessons learned from the creation of a prototype of the common catalogue**. This experience has shown a possible evolution about: (i) a possible extension of the data set with other attributes; (ii) a more accurate definition of the data model: which fields are mandatory, which ones are recommended, which ones are optional; (iii) define a set of rules to ensure data quality for incoming data; (iv) connect the prototype data model to up-to-date data sources.

The fourth chapter is the core of the blueprint: it contains the **technical features suggested to implement the common catalogue**. The catalogue is represented as a platform aimed at providing a unified system for managing research infrastructure data, enabling institutions to easily share information and collaborate on research activities. The catalogue's design and features, along with the development process are described in detail.

From the **technical point of view**, it is important to specify that the catalogue will be based on the process to **harvest existing information** on Una Europa research infrastructures. Starting from the information available at the institutional level, the catalogue foresees an automatic system to collect and display the existing data in a single place (web platform). This methodology is due to the need to decrease as much as possible the effort for the creation and the maintenance of the catalogue. For the universities that have not yet developed an internal catalogue of infrastructures, the blueprint provides guidelines and indications on how to create it.

Chapter five contains **suggestions for the university that still has not developed a catalogue at institutional level**. Jagiellonian University, Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne and University of Bologna describe their current situation regarding the catalogue of research infrastructures and future plans. The blueprint offers useful recommendations about the process to develop an internal catalogue: identify the research infrastructures existing; classify them according to their function, research area/field; create a database listing the University's research infrastructures; adopt a standard for information on research infrastructures in the catalogue; refer to a data model based on the Common European Research Information Format (CERIF) standard⁹.

The sixth chapter is aimed at **designing services that can be added to the catalogue of research infrastructure**. The main services listed are the following: (i) link between the RI identifier and publication/data outputs achieved by using the RI; (ii) link between the RI identifier and other infrastructure initiatives at different 'levels'; (iii) include and suggest the use of global RI PID; (iv) ensure the contact information of individual requesting how to get access to RI; (v) link to registration system (to use the facility) in the RI digital catalogue; (vi) link to a catalogue based on Una.Resin results, where the research teams from Una Europa Universities and the

⁹ The Common European Research Information Format (CERIF) is the comprehensive information model for the domain of scientific research. It is intended to support interchange of research information between and with CRISs.

transferable research results (from these research groups) would be available online for all kinds of public; (vii) technical support; (viii) user training (ix) notifications and alerts system.

The last chapter of the blueprint summarises the **next steps** that the Alliance needs to undertake to set up a common RIs catalogue:

- Approval by the governance of the institutions thereby making a long-term engagement of the individual institutions.
- An accurate assessment of the resources available at the institutions involved, in terms of personnel, budget, and infrastructure.
- Establish an adequate budget for the development and management of the shared research infrastructure catalogue, which considers the expenses for catalogue creation, continuous updating, promotion of the catalogue and training, and assistance to users.
- Establish the roles and responsibilities of the participating institutions, to ensure a balanced distribution of activities and efficient management of available resources across institutions.
- Identify potential financial risks associated with the project, such as decreased funding, increased maintenance costs, or loss of team members. It is necessary to plan how to deal with these risks and find alternative solutions to ensure the financial viability of the project.
- There is a need for a dedicated project and internal resources for setting up the digital catalogue, and the required operation.
- It is necessary to ensure systematic updates of RI information through regular data collection to keep the information updated so that the digital catalogue can be used maintained.
- The chapter including the technical recommendations for a future common catalogue should be integrated with a SWOT analysis that can support the selection of architecture, system and taxonomy that could be adopted for the common catalogue.
- A last point to consider in the future is the **interoperability of data**. Some research infrastructures could be already included in catalogues at institutional or regional/national level. The development of the Alliance's catalogue would not conflict with them: indeed, the data stored in the existing catalogues can be included at the same time also in other catalogues. This fact can increase the use of data thus positively affecting the use of research infrastructures and, consequently, improve the quality of research in the universities.

A final element to consider is to foresee the development of an **advanced blueprint** as suggested in the Strategy and action plan for sharing and opening up research and data infrastructures (cf. Section 1). The advanced version of the blueprint should address the above-mentioned bullets.

Pilot Action 2 - "Sharing Una Europa infrastructures: Museums and Digital Collections"

Introduction

The pilot project "Sharing Una Europa infrastructures: Museums and Digital collections" had the goal of testing a matchmaking process to effectively connect relevant entities and individuals. If successful, the project aimed to inspire a scalable format for the RIs in other research fields.

On the 30th of January the call for proposal for expressing interest in the pilot was launched and afterwards two workshops were organised, the first on the 30th of March 2023 and the second on the 4th of May 2023. 31 researchers/RIs managers from 9 universities (including the University of Zurich and the University of Paris-Nanterre) expressed interest in the pilot representing 27 infrastructures (see table below). 22 research infrastructures were involved in the workshops.

Infrastructure	University
AMS Historica	Unibo
Archéologie des Amériques (UMR8096)	Paris 1, CNRS
Bibliothèque interuniversitaire Cujas	Paris 1
Blendeff	KU Leuven
CollectiveAccess, Teneo	KU Leuven
Coordinator of the University collections	FUB
CS Digital	KU Leuven
Digital infrastructure of the department of Art History and Archaeology – UFR03	Paris 1
ENCODE (Bridging the Gap in Ancient Writing Cultures: ENhance COmpetences in the Digital Era)	Unibo
Finnish Museum of Natural History / Laboratory of Chronology	UH
FISCUS, the database of the project 'Fiscal Estate in Medieval Italy: Continuity and Change (Ninth-Twelfth Centuries)'	Unibo
Helda (institutional repository of University of Helsinki)	UH

Institute for the Study of the Transmission of Texts, Ideas and Images in Antiquity, the Middle Ages and the Renaissance	KU Leuven
KU Leuven Academic Heritage Collections (including about 30 collections) & KU Leuven Art Collections (including c. 10,000 artworks)	KU Leuven
Lovaniensia	KU Leuven
Magister Dixit and STUDIUM.AI	KU Leuven
Maurits Sabbe Library	KU Leuven
MemoBo - The Memoriali Project	Unibo
MSH Mondes	Université Paris Nanterre, CNRS, Paris 1
Museums and Collections Complutense University of Madrid	UCM
The database MuzUJ for the needs of recording and scientific study of artistic, natural and medical collections, etc.	JU
Trismegistos (also via ENCODE en STUDIUM)	KU Leuven
UCM - Ethnobotanical Collection	UCM
UMR 8215 Trajectoires	Paris 1
University Library System	Unibo
University of Zurich Museums and Collections	Zurich University
VIEW	KU Leuven

Main outcomes

Through the implementation of two matchmaking workshops, the project has achieved several important outcomes. The primary achievement of these workshops is the **establishment of a network** consisting of **RIs managers and responsible researchers in the field of Museums and digital collections**. These workshops allowed the participants to familiarize with each other, understand their specificities and needs, and define their mutual interests.

Under the guidance of a WP2 team, the established network goes beyond being a mere collection of contacts; it serves as a **solution-oriented network**. During the workshops, participants of the workshop have not only reflected on possible partnerships and collaborations, but also opened their minds to **new forms of collaboration that go beyond established frameworks** and target the **creation of a barrier-free research ecosystem**. As a result, the pilot project **raised participants' awareness** about the importance of opening RIs and the need to reflect on the openness and shareability of their data and services. The pilot also meant to inspire the **opening up to international partners and cooperation on a European level**, despite the middle and small size of the represented infrastructures.

The pilot project revealed a crucial lesson: establishing a network that goes beyond the mere exchange of experiences and best practices and includes joint collaborative activities based on the impetus provided by researchers and their research or educational projects.

Another important outcome of the pilot is therefore the **establishment of the direct connection between participating RIs and the Una Europa Self-Steering Committee of Cultural Heritage**.

This connection holds multiple benefits. Firstly, it enables the RIs to support activities that will be validated as part of the Una.Futura project action plan. But at the same time, it empowers the RIs to bring their own vision and suggest their own collaboration activities for research enhancement. In a long-term perspective, empowering of the RIs as the actors of international collaboration should **transform the institutional vision of infrastructure** from being solely a support system to becoming a **driving force behind research activities**. This change in perception can help to **improve the valorization of RIs** and can lead to the development of global solutions on openness and shareability by the policy makers.

In summary, the initial outcomes of the pilot project have demonstrated a high level of interest from RIs regarding collaboration and the potential for scaling up. The success of this pilot indicates that repeating and expanding such projects can generate interest from other types of infrastructures as well. Moreover, the **alignment of the initiatives discussed during the workshops with the action plans of Self-Steering Committees** holds great potential for reinforcing the research ecosystem and positioning RIs more effectively within institutional policies.

Recommendations and specific ideas for collaboration

Regarding the specific activities, various **ideas for collaboration** between RIs and the Self-Steering Committee of Cultural Heritage have emerged from the discussion on areas of mutual interest.

These include:

- Creating a "virtual museum" to showcase the RIs and their collections, providing visibility to their assets. This initiative could serve as an alternative to a joint catalogue,

considering that most RIs already have their own online catalogues or are part of broader national or European catalogue initiatives.

- Supporting Una Europa's participation in other projects such as the Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KIC) (EIT Culture & Creativity), as well as fostering important external partnerships with organisations and projects like ARCHE, European Heritage Hub, Europeana, Nemo, and others.
- Participating in joint calls, such as the "A European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage," which aims to develop RIs and their tools.
- Contributing to the organisation of joint events like the European Academic Heritage Day or the European Archaeology Days.
- Facilitating the exchange of best practices, particularly in collaborating with non-academic partners such as NGOs, institutions, businesses, and the wider civil society.

In addition to these collaborative actions, **research and education activities** were also considered.

For **research**, several joint actions were discussed:

- Positioning RIs as catalysts for new research projects, serving as bases for research activities, including PhD research. Specific calls could be launched to study RI collections or methodologies such as conservation, digitisation, AI imaging, and more. Una Europa RIs can provide support and inspiration to Transnational Research Teams (TRTs) established within the framework of Cultural Heritage Doctoral programmes.
- Supporting Una Europa Cultural Heritage in expanding their research topics to include Asia, Africa, and Latin America, as well as other interdisciplinary research projects aligned with Una Europa's focus areas.
- Assisting researchers in publishing their research in open access and facilitating joint publication initiatives.
- Hosting or participating in research conferences on relevant subjects.

In terms of **education**, collaboration between RIs and the Cultural Heritage Self-Steering Committee can also yield fruitful results:

- RIs can propose trainings or courses to develop specific skills, such as digitisation, imaging, data modelling, open science policies related to cultural heritage, and specialised humanities disciplines, 3D representations, AI applied to forms/images, study of ancient materials, and more. These trainings/courses could be offered as Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) or summer schools.
- Integrating these courses into existing PhD programme or incorporating them into future Masters programme

Pilot Action 2 - “Sharing Una Europa infrastructures: Genomics”

Introduction

The pilot project “Sharing Una Europa infrastructures: Genomics” has made the first steps towards potential future collaboration of inciting a barrier free collaboration between Una Europa RIs.

On the 30th of January 2023, the call for proposal for expressing interest in the pilot was launched and afterwards two workshops were organised, the first on the 23rd of March 2023 and the second on the 4th of May 2023. 17 researchers/RIs managers from 6 universities (including the University of Zurich) expressed interest in the pilot representing 11 infrastructures (see table below). 10 research infrastructures were involved in the workshops.

Infrastructure	University
Laboratory of Reproductive Genomics	KU Leuven
Genomics Core Leuven	KU Leuven
Animal and Human Health Engineering (A2H)	KU Leuven
FIBEr, KU Leuven Core Facility for Biomechanical Experimentation	KU Leuven
UCM Genomics Unit	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Microbiomics Unit	University of Bologna
Animal and Food Genomics Group	University of Bologna
aDNA Lab	University of Bologna
Edinburgh Clinical Research Facility	University of Edinburgh
FIMM – Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland	University of Helsinki
Functional Genomics Centre Zurich	University of Zurich

Background

Through the two workshops organised, a **network of RIs managers and responsible researchers in relation to Genomics was established**. These workshops allowed the participants to familiarize with each other, understand their expertise and needs, and define their mutual interests. The established interest group foresees not only the sharing of the

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017416.

experience or best practices, but also the exploration of future joint collaborative activities in any possible form. For this aim, the impulse from this expert group and the willingness to share their activities is key. At the same time, the RIs were empowered to bring their own vision, suggest their own activities, and promote collaborative use.

Main outcomes

The participants in the pilot study of Genomics had the opportunity to present their research infrastructure and (core) facility. This was a useful exchange as it gave opportunity to get to know each other, to reflect on their own existing activities and practices and on possible collaborative use of the infrastructure. It was emphasised to strive for harmonisation and centralisation, and to connect to European level of infrastructure. Genomics research managers expressed their interest in various areas including, sharing knowledge and expertise, protocols, pipelines/guidelines, quality standards, resources, automation techniques, experience-sharing on equipment. From here, it was also strongly felt that there was a need to identify specialisation of themes as a group to work further. Research managers were particularly keen to identify opportunities for training in the field such as pipeline automation, and bioinformatics.

While open research activities cannot be fully applied to areas such as genomics because of barriers in sharing actual research data, research managers highlighted the importance of Open Research activities paying much more attention on for instance, FAIR data principles and metadata production. They were also specially interested to promote physical mobility of RI staff to visit on-sites research infrastructure which then in turn provide some solutions to the barriers in opening data, but also to observe ways of operation at the infrastructure level. There was also an interest to explore ways to promote the use of research infrastructure for students so that this activity can take a form as educational programme.

It was found very important to **create synergies with the action plans of One Health Self-Steering Committee**. In this regard, WP2 presented the strategies and activities in relation to research and data infrastructures to all members of the One Health SSC in Leiden on the 8th of June. The OH SSC members showed interest to follow up on the Genomics pilot activities that were initiated under Una.Resin, and proposed to expand the mapping of RIs in relation to One Health areas. Generally, the group expressed its interest to support the activities of the Genomics network of RIs for discussing genomics-related areas of interest as mentioned above.

Although it is too early to fully assess the impact of the pilot project, it can be said that it has already influenced its main stakeholders, i.e. RIs managers and responsible researchers. Their involvement in the pilot project has not only enhanced their learning about the available expertise and good practices it also **opened their minds to new forms of collaboration** that go beyond their own existing established frameworks. The pilot has also **raised the participants awareness regarding the opening of the RIs** and the **need to reflect on the consequences of openness and shareability** of their data and services.

Empowering of the RIs as the actors of international research collaboration by opening and sharing RIs could **transform the institutional vision** on infrastructure from being solely a support for the local RI ecosystem to becoming a **driving force able to stimulate collaborative research activities**. This change in perception can help to improve the valorization of RIs leading to the development of global solutions on openness and shareability by the policy makers.

Most of the RIs that participated in the workshop have national partners. The pilot meant to inspire the **opening to international partners** and **cooperation on a European level** of the medium and small sized represented infrastructures.

To sum up, the **first outcomes** of the pilot showed that the RIs represented in the workshops are interested in exchanging knowledge and good practices on genomics which on the longer term could initiate new collaborations. The scaling up of this pilot can generate the interest from other themes under One Health and other types of infrastructures. In order to reinforce the RIs eco-system, it is crucial to align RIs' collaborations with the action plans of Self-Steering Committees.

Recommendations and specific ideas for collaboration

These are the first sets of recommendations arising from the workshops and the research infrastructure cluster who have initiated the group setting. Several additional comments were added arising from the experts.

- **Tools** to allow the research community **to learn and explore the range of RIs** available across the Alliance and to provide a common information point. This will allow to **identify complementary assets and enhance RI visibility to potential users and collaborators**.
- Connection of people to **promote contacts across RI staff, promote contact with academic researchers and matchmaking for RIs** in specific research domains. This can take the form of articles, newsletters, and success stories that can be shared through digital platforms.
- Enhance the role of RI in **fostering Open Research and FAIR data management**. Development of common guidelines on operationalization of FAIR principles.
- **Assess costing & funding models**; secure funding in order to cover access fees; stimulate researchers applying for grants to cover RI costs; allocate seed-funding for initial research collaborations. It would be important to adapt pricing systems and business models for the Alliance members by taking multiple perspectives into account (e.g., government regulations and user perspectives). The difficulty in managing different expectations on costing from different stakeholders (i.e., users, institutional funders, and funding agencies) was discussed as a critical point.
- **Strengthening knowledge & skills including in RI management**, e.g., through **mutual learning; training; and micro-credentials**. As aforementioned, there is an interest to

promote **staff mobility and interdisciplinary research**. Here, also to work very closely with the SSC One Health to integrate the proposed actions into their visions and objectives.

- Policies & strategies to overcoming barriers: co-design and promote an Una Europa charter for Research Infrastructures that will encourage the adoption of common general principles. This can be concretised through undertaking a common advocacy action to strengthen RIs.

Potential way forward of Pilot Action 2 in relation to the future R&I priority areas

This initiative on RIs community building aligns with one of the activities that is proposed in the Deliverable 2.2 “A shared Una Europa strategy for sharing RIs” (cf. Section 1). More specifically, this refers to the Pillar 1 - Action 2 where the community building of research infrastructures is proposed. This activity will take several steps subject to levels of funding and the ambitions of the governance model:

- organisation of theme-specific RIs matchmaking workshops and events to identify common interests and paths towards sharing the research infrastructure and create synergies;
- scaling of the matchmaking to other focus areas, create virtual thematic networks of infrastructure to give public visibility, organise in-person seminars, workshops and events, and stimulate the interest of researchers to apply common funding proposals;
- create synergies with other university alliances to build upon the identified specific thematic areas.

This activity, along with the other activities described in Section 1, was proposed to the Una Europa BoD and RSG and could be taken forward through, for example, internal resources of the universities. A process aimed at setting the R&I priorities of the Alliance was launched in June 2023 and will be finalised in November 2023, through an internal consultation (based on a two-step survey) at the governance level in each institution.

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